

Non-Fungible Tokens Value with Metaverse and Blockchain Gaming

A Dissertation Presented in Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements for the Degree of
Doctor of Computer Science

by

William Mcilhargey Jr

Department of Doctoral Studies, Colorado Technical University

November 2021

Committee Members

Alexa Schmitt, PhD, Chair

Jeffrey Butler, PhD, Committee Member

Cynthia Calongne, DCS, Committee Member

Signature Page

Non-Fungible Tokens Value with Metaverse and Blockchain Gaming

William Mcilhargey Jr

Approved by Doctoral Committee:

DocuSigned by:
Alexa Schmitt, PhD January 10, 2023
EEBAEF14B0C6400...
Dissertation Chair Date

DocuSigned by:
Jeffrey Butler, PhD January 10, 2023
3C8D88D8CCD146C...
Committee Member Date

DocuSigned by:
Cynthia Calongue, DCS January 12, 2023
84904501EB6349F...
Committee Member Date

Abstract

Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs) had shown significant hype since 2021 and had gained popularity as a way to trade value as an asset. The study opportunity was to investigate NFTs within the blockchain platform to identify how adding utility and combining the utility inside a metaverse would hold the value of NFTs. This qualitative exploratory study investigated how NFTs can be monetized and used by creating a market to provide the demand. This research study examined the NFTs and reviewed how they could be developed into something useful. The monetization of new markets was an underlying question that was researched as part of this study to determine if they could be created and if there was an effective way to influence utility to generate value. An exploratory research design was used to survey 50 respondents to uncover concepts from blockchain to metaverse research. The results aligned with the perspective that NFTs appeared not to follow what a traditional asset would stick to. Based on the findings, NFTs could create new markets and entice demand by relying on unique and limited characteristics defined throughout this research.

Keywords: non-fungible token, metaverse, blockchain, games, qualitative study

Acknowledgments

I want to thank the following people, without whom I would not have been able to complete this research and without whom I would not have made it through my doctorate!

My research supervisor, Dr. Alexa Schmitt, was essential to completing my dissertation and ensured my success by keeping me on track to complete my dissertation and all the help with the revisions to the dissertation. Without her continued efforts, I would not have met my requirements to complete the program, and thank you again for all the hard work and help to push me to complete the study!

Also, to Microsoft for providing the flexibility and resources while I was on the journey of working towards my degree and heads down focused on the research.

Also, the DEEPSPACE community for participating in the study, providing insights to drive the research discussed, and providing future research.

And to my parents, Kathy and Bill, for all the support and encouragement driving me to continue my education, supporting me in my initiatives, and encouraging me to obtain my degrees. I have finally reached the terminal degree and can take a break!

And finally, to my wife, Linsey, thanks for all your support during the journey, without which I would have stopped these studies long ago. Thank you for understanding the amount of time this would take to complete the program, and looking forward to sharing the extra time back with each other!

Table of Contents

Chapter 1: Introduction	1
Study Opportunity	2
Study Purpose	3
Research Question	5
Conceptual Framework.....	5
Significance of the Study.....	8
Researcher Positionality and Reflexivity.....	9
Delimitations and Limitations	10
Definition of Terms	11
Chapter Summary	13
Chapter 2: Review of the Literature	14
Literature Search Strategies.....	14
Metaverse and NFT Blockchain Concepts.....	16
Trusted System Review	17
Decentralization Risks.....	20
Sequencing and Transactional Considerations.....	21
Technological Advances on the Platform	23
Implementation of the Blockchain Framework	24
Authentication and Security	25
NFT Centralization Risk & Mitigation Strategies.....	27
Metaverse Vision	29

Data Interconnecting	31
Media Attention.....	33
ERC-721.....	33
Gaps in the Literature	34
Conclusions	35
Chapter Summary	36
Chapter 3: Methodology, Design, and Methods	38
Research Methodology and Design	39
Population, Sample, and Participant Recruitment	40
Data Collection Instrumentation and Procedures	42
Data Analysis and Procedures.....	44
Trustworthiness	45
Ethical Assurances.....	47
Chapter Summary	48
Chapter 4: Findings	50
Description of the Study Sample	50
Results.....	52
Discussion of Study Findings.....	57
Chapter Summary	59
Chapter 5: Discussion and Conclusions	61
Limitations of Study Findings.....	62
Interpretation of Study Findings.....	63

Practice Implications of Study Findings	66
Researcher Reflections	67
Recommendations for Further Research.....	69
Recommendation 1.....	69
Recommendation 2.....	70
Recommendation 3.....	71
Conclusion.....	71
References	75
Appendix A: Survey Questions.....	95

List of Figures

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework of <i>NFT Ecosystem for Creating Value within a Metaverse</i>	8
Figure 2 <i>Comparing Experience Interacting with NFTs and Participant's Age</i>	52

Chapter 1: Introduction

Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs) had shown significant hype since 2021 and had been around on the blockchain to store value and represent a digital asset; (Pinto-Gutiérrez et al., 2022). The hype had a way to build and demonstrated potential monetization with the release of NFT marketplaces allowing the easy buying, selling, and transferring of NFT ownership data by capturing NFT metadata and then provided a frictionless yield of digital assets. As with every way of storing value, the method in the digital world was also vulnerable to exploitation.

Blockchain technology power came from transparency and was empowered by the timestamps and cryptography it provides (Rajguru, 2021). A foolproof peer-to-peer network ensured transparency without a middle-man agency overseeing the process, which further empowered the process. This further accelerated the use of gaming within the blockchain, where decentralized applications could be further expanded and allowed for decentralized voting to take effect.

To prevent one entity from running an entire platform, decentralized, autonomous applications allowed a community to run an entire platform which were free from the control and interference of a single authority. These decentralized applications were an emerging application model that would be further expanded over the next 10 years and could provide a bridge to bring new initiatives, such as gaming models to the blockchain, on a decentralized path (Antal et al., 2021). A decentralized application could ensure anonymity, community buy-in, and transacting data and structure privacy. One key area in business in these decentralized environments would be getting the business rules to work with the transactions and apply the concepts as part of the overall processes (Subramanian et al., 2020). Blockchain could facilitate

transparency and traceability for transactions that occurred on the ledger. Financial regulations could be brought up as a result, and these key areas could be further directed and impacted over time.

NFTs were seen as non-utility-based assets, and finding utility to these contract-based approaches were essential to further expansion (Shen et al., 2021). Given the increased interest of bitcoin and blockchain technology, attention in these platforms had expanded over the years, causing an increase in value and total trading to unseen values. Having sold ownership of digitized assets leads to being able to trade ownership and further gather additional revenue from the transactions of these sales. However, bad actors could further contribute to providing seemingly useless NFTs (Valeonti et al., 2021). Looking forward, more research would be needed to further look into NFTs to understand their utility and use. Extending the metaverse would allow for a simple business model with mass customizations and enables an e-commerce site accessible to millions of customers over the Internet (Wagner & Cozmiuc, 2022).

Study Opportunity

The study opportunity was to further investigate NFTs within the blockchain platform to identify how adding utility and combining the utility inside a metaverse would hold the value of NFTs (Davis et al., 2009). Even the concept of loading NFTs inside the metaverse could arrive by big players allowing a more affordable option and easier access over time (Valeonti et al., 2021). Four hundred and ninety million dollars was the latest value the NFTs had generated in 2021 alone (Muddasar & Bagui, 2021). One use case for artists would be digital art, but one difficulty was standing out amongst all the collections. The research would further be reviewed to identify ones with utility or provide extra weight on top of the art to see if those hold value

over a more extended period. The intelligent contracts act like escrows and instead utilize oracles, providing a source of truth when interacting with the blockchain to confirm the digital asset (Ojog, 2021). The blockchain would further prove asset ownership, allowing for trading or other utility functions when interacting with the purchase.

An ERC-721 is a framework created for the Ethereum blockchain that mentioned the type of token, the NFT, was unique and would have a different value from the same contract (Palmisano et al., 2022). Implementing a well-architected ERC-721 standard for NFT tokens would ensure consistency across the platform and data interoperability, allowing the digital assets to be valuable and transactive on the platforms (Palmisano et al., 2022). The assets would be used for tickets, gaming, or digital art to establish a marketplace to further transact upon and communicate between a buyer and a seller to establish a relationship (Caldarelli, 2022). The economy involved could be further exploited depending on the buyer or seller, and this could be leveraged depending on the value of the asset going forward.

Study Purpose

The purpose of this qualitative exploratory study was to investigate how NFTs could be monetized and used by creating a market to provide the demand. This research study would examine this new space and understand how it would be reviewed to be developed into something useful. For example, NFTs could be used in a game world to connect users to in-game experiences, representing a metaverse interaction with NFTs or SFTs. A qualitative research approach was used to understand the characteristics of the social phenomena on why NFTs may or may not be more valuable as a utility in a metaverse environment (Liu et al., 2020). One could acquire additional research on what was viewed as necessary information in

assessing NFTs and buying into them, and to produce value while then further researching trends and data from the platforms that host these collections to collaborate with the data presented (Leon et al., 2014).

As part of the study, the target population was the social media and community members familiar with cryptocurrency and NFTs. A typical audience understanding the blockchain technologies could have an impact on how the technology was adopted and it was used. The population was further focused on gaming enthusiasts whom would know the platforms targeted as part of the metaverse. An audience with relevant information would further understand and address the concepts. The overall criteria must match the purpose, determining how NFTs could be monetized and used by creating a market to provide the demand. In addition to these requirements, the participants must understand how to interact with the blockchain. They would be familiar with the social community so they could see the survey to participate. These were the basic requirements to join and participate in the study. The estimated size of the target population was well over 10,000 community members.

The desired study sample size was approximately 50 participants to provide qualitative survey responses. The sample size of 50 participants was sought to provide enough of a selective sample to have a collective response that provided a reflective voice. Based on other major case studies using samplings of this type a range of 30 to 50 samples were sufficient to obtain an accurate outcome (Marshall et al., 2013). A selective sampling method was used for this study and the final sample size was 44. The written text acquired from survey responses consisted of multiple-choice responses and fill-in-the-blank responses to provide data that

would inform the research questions. A Google Form was used to collect the responses where Google Forms stored the data into Google Sheets.

The collected data could be further researched to address the research question and then would allow further digging into additional questions, ranging from NFTs to blockchain, to metaverse topics. Similar exploratory studies were performed in the esports gaming sectors, which tested similar foundations and assumptions from a foundational perspective (Ke et al., 2022).

Research Question

The study research questions would help further address a matter related to a practice-oriented problem in the field of computer science by digging into the more profound questions in the blockchain field. To address the study purpose, primary and sub-research questions were developed, which provided additional themes and concepts as part of the study.

Q1

How could NFTs be monetized and used by creating a market to provide the demand?

Q1a. As markets mature, could comparable NFTs be evaluated to determine the effectiveness of utility NFTs?

Q1b. What unique characterizations and market conditions would be required?

Conceptual Framework

The blockchain platform handles the solution's backend structure and technical layout. The blockchain was an irrefutable transaction store that holds the historical data. This was part of an overall connected infrastructure that could handle the paradigm between the answers for this to work (Risius, 2017). The platform could further realize the transactions and aspects as a

result. This would tie the blockchain to the metaverse, which would be explained in the next section.

The metaverse was an exciting topic that was still highly debated, and the definitions are an immense three-dimensional world where avatars could interact (Davis et al., 2009). This was also discussed on what avatars and other assets and resources, as NFTs, would look like and how they interconnect across social media and social gameplay. These would connect to the blockchain by interconnecting multiple projects and approaches. In addition, then the metaverse would interconnect to NFTs.

Non-Fungible tokens then would rely on the blockchain to transact. Still, they were the front interface of the avatars that are part of the metaverse and work closely with these together (Pinto-Gutiérrez et al., 2022), using NFTs as a form of property to transact between players and present into avatars and profiles. These were all related concepts that were disparate and then interconnected as well.

The customers, or players, utilized these concepts and interacted with these disparate tools to bring these technologies together and provide the demand. They used them to transact and transfer value on these toolsets. In addition, they evaluated the need for acceptable and unacceptable concepts and drove the market accordingly. Platforms such as OpenSea, NiftyGate, super rare, and Foundation provided the markets and the tools used to trade the NFTs and allowed the users to set the prices (Vasan et al., 2022).

There were integrated components that help drove the usage and awareness of these platforms. For example, the marketing efforts used by these platforms could help drive demand and awareness of the blockchain, NFTs, and metaverse concepts to help convince customers to

utilize these platforms to solidify these concepts further. In addition, the gaming concept could provide more than just an avatar but actual need and utility to the associated NFTs. Finally, the economics and monetization of these platforms offered incentives and could help drive behaviors and results. The customers were interconnected with the entire ecosystem between the blockchain, the NFTs, and the metaverse.

As depicted in Figure 1, the concept diagram noted the interfaces between the metaverse, the blockchain, and the non-fungible tokens. The platforms were all interconnected but disparate pieces as part of the research. These demonstrated how the conceptual elements of the framework could independently work together to make up the entire cryptocurrency ecosystem. One could achieve harmony in a well-connected system by connecting these disparate systems.

Figure 1

Conceptual Framework of NFT Ecosystem for Creating Value within a Metaverse.

Note. The conceptual framework focused on a gaming blockchain ecosystem with a lens on the metaverse and non-fungible tokens dynamics.

Significance of the Study

This study was significant as it was an original contribution to NFTs and blockchain technology, focusing on utility. NFTs have become a popular commodity; for example, from 2020 to 2021, the NFT market went from \$181,121 to well over \$38 million in 2021 in total daily sales (Pinto-Gutiérrez et al., 2022). Still, the utility NFTs were the ones that would further see the value from now on in monetization, and further research should additionally provide these or disprove this. It was essential to understand as these areas were researched and built to

understand how NFTs could be further impacted by the result of useless or valuable daily projects, attempting to gain users' attention on a massive scale.

Researcher Positionality and Reflexivity

Since 2012, one of my interests and passions had been researching blockchain technologies. Blockchain technology was a decentralized technology based on computing power that allowed verified transactions to occur based on untrusted events within an event (Bhargava, 2019a, 2019b). The idea was that these technologies could be industry-wide, turn the course on what would be possible, and revamp many industries with how transactions occur. The provided framework had proven to work in many situations; it also covered other conditions, such as environmental impact, depending on the incentives one tried to target as part of these events. Finally, the recent introduction to expanding the framework to include new standards such as ERC-721, NFTs, had also caused a massive explosion due to these new capabilities. As the industry continued to adopt these new technologies, all the applications that could be used also remain to be seen. One industry, such as the gaming industry, were jumping on board, and some platforms, such as Binance, are investing over \$1 billion in growth money into the ecosystem. (Chain, 2022). There was a massive opportunity in this space, and everyone was early who joined, as it was only just beginning.

The research topic aimed to research how NFTs could be monetized and used by creating a market to provide the demand. NFTs have become a significant hit as of 2021, so much so that they were the year's word during 2021 (voanews, 2021). The plan behind NFTs was a piece of property or a smart contract on the blockchain that, ideally, no one else has, creating a unique collection. It is one type of event that has occurred and had only ever been

minted once, and that was all there ever was. Recently, there was a picture of a monkey (BAYC, 2022) or an access token to an exclusive event. One unique area I was researching with a topic of using NFTs within the metaverse and using them as a brilliant, upgradeable asset within this ecosystem. NFTs, once minted, could never be touched. Their attributes or properties cannot be modified or connected; however, a new concept of smart or upgradeable NFTs was being experimented with, making the idea inaccurate in the context (Huang, 2021).

My biggest strengths as a researcher were experience and an active project that I had worked on with a team of members for over a year in this field. By leveraging industry experience and using live data, I could bring this to the models and paper to further add credibility and real-life data analysis to define further and model expectations. Overall, the space was still new and being developed, and there was a lot of opportunity for research and development in the areas due to this continued research. To mitigate any potential bias I could bring to my study, and I would follow appropriate research methods for data collection and analysis to reveal the findings of participants. I would practice reflexivity and look to the literature to further analyze the study findings.

Delimitations and Limitations

The research within this space covers the blockchain and the metaverse facets within constrained limitations and, as a result, were constrained to a particular vision. The scope further focused on the utility in fashion and how it could interact with marketing, gaming, and the economic impact of the interoperability of these components.

The limitations in this study were focused on not going beyond the mentioned boundaries and, as such, would disregard other types of NFTs outside the ERC-721 standard

and not on the standard OpenSea trading platform. By ensuring a consistent and trading platform that would be analyzed and reviewed, these boundaries could be further limited to a focused research topic and thereby obtain a more focused address to the research topic. Going to non-standards or new standards and off-marketplaces could curve the results and provide too many variables that would skew the results of the NFT values, which would further result in ineffective data and inaccurate results in the research process. In the blockchain, anyone could create a contract, whether it would follow a standard or not, as long as it followed the correct code for the particular blockchain. As long as the marketplace, or a custom marketplace, was created to read the blockchain and present the data, then the digital assets could be displayed to the end-users. Following the standards made it easier for transferability and interoperability across digital wallets and standardized tools and marketplaces as those are more likely to be able to display and work with end-users.

Definition of Terms

The terms within the research study were included to define how they are used and included and incorporated to help the readers better understand the core concepts, technology, focus, and scope of the research study relating to the topics. The key terms were further defined to align with the current industry knowledge and aspects of current trends and recent research performed.

Blockchain

The blockchain was an irrefutable transaction store that holds the historical data and data across solutions. This was a part of an overall connected infrastructure that could handle the paradigm between the answers for this to work (Risius, 2017).

Metaverse

The metaverse was an exciting topic that was still highly debated, and the current definitions are an immense three-dimensional world where avatars could interact (Davis et al., 2009). This was also being discussed highly on what this looks like and how it interconnects across social media and social gameplay.

Non-Fungible Tokens

NFTs relied on the blockchain to transact. Still, they were the front interface of the avatars that were part of the metaverse and work closely with these together (Pinto-Gutiérrez et al., 2022), using NFTs as a form of property to transact between players and present into avatars and profiles.

Smart Contract

Smart Contracts were automated processes that occur on a blockchain that could facilitate a transfer of a digital asset or good (Francesca Dal et al., 2020).

Decentralized Finance

Decentralized Finance (DeFi) describes financial applications built on blockchain technologies. The inherent trust was the underlying capability where it was put into the hands of the consumers and allowed them to transact between each other and only with each other (Ojog, 2021).

Utility

Utility is the concept of intangible tokens and could be fungible or non-fungible assets representing access to a product or service and serving as a paying function (Paajala et al., 2022).

Chapter Summary

Gaming in the metaverse offered a unique perspective with NFTs. Throughout the chapter, the topics covered the unique opportunities within the space that were researched throughout the paper to better understand how they interact and depend upon each other. NFTs could provide more value when utility was added, and as they do, they give a method for stored value. They act as a digital asset and potentially cause fear of missing out on an opportunity for the customer. Within the next section of the study, the literature review delves into the bigger topics and terms reviewed and discussed throughout the study. The evidence displayed as part of the research could help reinforce the background of what has been collected and would be presented in later sections.

Chapter 2: Review of the Literature

The purpose of this qualitative exploratory study was to investigate how NFTs could be monetized and used by creating a market to provide the demand. The research study would examine this new space and better understand how this could be reviewed to be developed into something useful. For example, NFTs could be used in a game world to connect users to in-game experiences, representing metaverse interactions with NFTs or SFTs. The study opportunity was to investigate NFTs within the blockchain platform to identify how adding utility and combining the utility inside a metaverse would hold the value of NFTs (Davis et al., 2009). The concept of loading NFTs inside the metaverse could arrive by big players allowing more affordable and accessible access options over time (Valeonti et al., 2021). The metaverse interconnects between the blockchain and NFTs, providing value to the customers using the connected platforms to provide utility. By providing a utility to the NFTs, there could be an underlying market demand increasing the buying pressure and value to the general concept of the gaming platform.

Throughout this research, the following topics would be covered, Literature Search Strategies, Metaverse, and NFT Blockchain Concepts Trusted System Review, Decentralization Risks, Sequencing, and Transactional Considerations, Technological Advances on the Platform, Implementation of the Blockchain Framework, Authentication and Security, Qualitative Review, Metaverse Vision, Data Interconnecting, and Media Attention.

Literature Search Strategies

Blockchain frameworks and methodologies were a relatively newer concept, and research was exploding in blockchain technologies, NFTs, and, more recently, Metaverse

technology. These concepts have exploded in public internet searches, and researchers have begun to pick up upon these over the years to dig into them to see what they are made up of. Blockchain platforms were one key term used to help identify scholarly articles. Another critical reference was searching for cryptocurrency NFT to search for hits on related technology and discussions that have been peer-reviewed. Another key opportunity for research was metaverse and looking through articles related to these topics. Finding resources related to these terms was critical to finding relevant and timely research to build a case for the analysis. In addition, blockchain trust and oracles were used to identify areas of interest in critical segments relating to compromise and alignment. One database search that was used was the Computer Science Database in ProQuest, where significant search terms were used when digging through these literature cases were, Blockchain platforms, Blockchain identity, Blockchain applications, decentralization platforms, bitcoin blockchain, cryptocurrency effects, enterprise platforms, blockchain, non-fungible tokens, NFTs and blockchain, metaverse, regulations and blockchain, blockchain analysis, blockchain immutability, blockchain smart city.

The scholarship keywords and phrases were also used to identify the ACM Digital Library to help review additional resources where blockchain identity and blockchain cryptocurrency terms were used. Reviewing other words such as monetization cryptocurrency and marketing NFTs helped find critical articles relating to open markets on cryptocurrency and research within the blockchain space relevant to this research.

Having reviewed the search terms and critical criteria covering NFTs, blockchain resources, and metaverse conversations, one must now investigate the literature review to

understand the metaverse and NFT concepts and the relevant research associated with these components.

Metaverse and NFT Blockchain Concepts

Utilizing the metaverse components within the research criteria was essential due to the areas that understand these components. Using the metaverse and transmedia storytelling was becoming a popular way to expand upon engaging the audience of gamers to engage in this space (İldaş, 2022). By utilizing digital passports and traveling the world, one could quickly engage the audience to make the buyer feel part of the universe rather than just seeing the universe.

Bringing the metaverse to the blockchain was an additional concept that overcomes a different challenge of getting a decentralized world for gamers to interact with while inside this alternate world. By decentralizing the metaverse and putting it on top of a blockchain, a gaming metaverse could further impact the gamers by providing an immersive virtual space and experience that would allow for virtual commerce, application design, and interactivity (Shen et al., 2021). Virtual exchanges could further facilitate in-game purchases such as NFTs to produce utility to these assets on the blockchain to expand in-game transactions and use for in-game help. The concept chart in Chapter 1 further informed the study of the key stakeholders and industry terms used to connect the components and bring the study together. As demonstrated in Figure 1 of Chapter 1, it was essential to understand how the dimensions work together. Blockchain technology was an immutable ledger of records that could be sliced up into portions and given as a value, for example, Bitcoin. It could be coded to execute automatic transactions on the network, such as Ethereum, which would allow for tying assets as a record of ownership,

for example, NFTs (Cornelius, 2021). The concept of further establishing NFTs, making them a source of truth, and then tying them to a metaverse would additionally allow these pieces to be linked together. The historical details of transactions on the network that miners maintain allowed for a consensus of trust to occur, allowing the contracts to be further executed and evolve (L. Wang et al., 2021).

An ERC-721 was a framework created for Ethereum blockchain where a unique asset could have a different value from the same contract (Palmisano et al., 2022). Implementing a well-architected ERC-721 standard for NFT tokens could ensure consistency across the platform and data interoperability, allowing the digital assets to be valuable and transactive on the platforms (Palmisano et al., 2022). The support could be used for tickets, gaming, or digital art to establish a marketplace to transact further and communicate between a buyer and a seller to establish a relationship (Caldarelli, 2022). The economy could be further exploited depending on the buyer or seller, which could be leveraged depending on the asset's value in the future.

Trusted System Review

As with any trusted system, trust must be earned, especially in a new given technology that was meant to be overridden. Blockchain and trust could be had hand-in-hand, but it had to be explicitly granted due to direct conviction (Liu, 2019). The underlying belief of the model must be inherently trustworthy and represented. As a result, otherwise, the model broke down quickly, whereas, in the traditional model, banks and regulated industries' trust was relied upon in those models. In contrast, if trust broke down in those models, then the same occurrence would happen in these models (Li et al., 2021). User perception was also crucial to the system's trust; inherently, a blockchain-based system would be accepted if it was seen as trustworthy,

convenient, and valuable. Building this system based upon the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and a trust model, as previous studies had indicated, would work for user acceptance as long as the trust was built (Shrestha et al., 2021).

In a perceived trust model, entire infrastructure and systems could be upgraded and agreed upon based on the trust model. For example, if 51% of the node operators agreed on an infrastructure system upgrade, it would move to a version upgrade and only process transactions from the newest software revision (Caldarelli, 2022).

Gaming Aspects of Blockchain

Creating a sustainable environment on the blockchain was a new challenge. More specifically, the challenges of developing a modern society that was both resource-efficient and trustworthy was a tricky balance to further expand upon (Predescu et al., 2021). Adding gamification to the marketplace was essential; marketplace design patterns in blockchain technologies could help be implemented in a decentralized public database which would help store computational problems and stores concurrently (Palma et al., 2018). In addition, game theory further proves what works and what does not by sending the data to the edge and allowing it to scale appropriately. A detection-based-oriented approach could further ensure a strategy aligned with the proper economics (Li et al., 2020).

Decentralized Finance (DeFi) allowed for creating gaming, financial, and many different types of applications on the blockchain. It put the financial transactions into the hands of the consumers rather than the responsibilities of the banks and eradicates the third parties. Gaming was an exciting aspect as it opens the door for in-game currency and gaming tokens to allow users to perform micro-transactions at scale and with ease. In a study by (Kuzma et al.,

2022), targeting paying gamers inside free-to-play games tended to be the best choice to maximize game revenue. Having reduced the friction to capture this revenue would likely increase the revenue the fastest (Kuzma et al., 2022).

Protocol and Design

In reviewing the overall protocol design of the blockchain platform, the challenges in the blockchain network would be essential to be considered as part of the overall protocol design (Yuan et al., 2018). As part of a comprehensive review, it was crucial to consider the challenges in the design phase. The nature of the protocol was to ensure there were situations where this could leverage as a result of providing a developed pragmatic approach accordingly. For example designing the blockchain strategy on a centralized process, such as the Internet of Things (IoT), could be challenging; client/server models, while centralized, could be decentralized using IoT architecture and gateways allowing methods to talk to each other and build out more streamlined and efficient architectures (Atlam et al., 2018). These processes must be further accounted for and redesigned to support, such a case study. Progression with communication service plans and proposing a virtual network with the proper bandwidth was critical to ensuring the appropriate distributed systems and reducing the delay mean at the time of supervision for the services (Mahato et al., 2021).

Trust was essential and critical to the node's reputation to ensure a blockchain network's highly available nature status. Due to the decentralized nature and untrusted quality of the network, if a node is constantly down, out of data, and has a poor network, these factors would be considered for it to be viewed on the web. As a result, this was where node reputation was taken into consideration. A node reputation score was a score where several

factors were calculated to provide a weighted average over time. The better the score, the more it was weighted to ensure it would be allowed to join the network. The reputation-driven node elimination PBFT (RE-PBFT) was proposed to optimize PBFT consensus (Jiang et al., 2022). This consensus prevented an established blockchain network from occurring and ensured a fair handshake across the node operators.

Decentralization Risks

Considering the Internet was increasingly accessible, this decentralized technology could be of even further importance to ensure this was accessible regardless of where the users were or what technologies were being used. For example, vehicles needed the internet or some connectivity to an IoT network to stay connected to Roadside Units to ensure instructions were received and transmitted (Qasim Ali Arain; Memon, 2018).

In addition to making the application location-aware, it was essential to ensure that the various cloud services and microservices were interconnected. Artificial Intelligence (AI) and cloud services reduced the investments needed in intelligence technologies due to research streams (Case et al., 2019). The challenges in this type of system were essential to ensure an immediate benefit was determined as a result, and then when that was realized, it again was determined. System regards were technical knowledge and exposing preconditions to joining a mobile system while identifying information where immediate benefits are significant (Mamais, 2017). The benefits could then be reviewed as appropriate and followed from here. There is also a result that in similar systems, this idea of immutability was also essential. In the healthcare field, healthcare information entered within a blockchain could become immutable.

The information provided could be focused on as a data provider, and data collection supplied throughout as part of the overall stream (Shen, 2019). There were many competitors in this space, and weeding out the real value within this space and the incoherent worthless tokens. The idea with these risks could show how new industries designed with danger in mind, such as a casino, could then adapt and reflect to support customers within a consistent framework by providing virtual gaming and casino services over the framework (Da-Yin & Wang, 2018; Liao & Wang, 2018).

Sequencing and Transactional Considerations

Initializing a sequence to a blockchain could take many things, such as network integrity, distributed power, security, business processes, etc. (Stoica, 2019). Just starting and ensuring the platform had what was needed to develop and grow a community, but that was where the open-source-style community of a platform comes in. Ethereum technology could provide innovative solutions for decentralized technologies and user privacy and data management (De Domenico, 2019). Sequencing and processing applications with the right quality of service were critical to succeeding as a result (Xu et al., 2020).

A different model was being used to power the proposed application. As a result, the gamification of marketplace part pants could contribute computational power and creativity towards a single goal in a decentralized way (Palma, 2018). The gamification model incentivized miners to help run and verify the platform through transactions. In essence, blockchain miners were incentivized to verify transactions; however, they are not incentivized to help users enforce written transactions (Pappalardo, 2018). The benefits helped keep these microtransactions running on the platform, incentivizing the community to power the platform.

The rest of the community could focus on using the forum and pay the service providers for using the platform. For example, the cost to run these platforms could be attributed to blockchain solutions, which cost micropayments or require these solutions to use the Bitcoin-based blockchain decentralized applications and ensured they are correctly working (Knirsch, 2019).

As another example, when Initial Coin Offerings (ICOs) were initially launched, newly minted collections were further researched and was shown to have enormous risk and speed of investment by investors (Liao & Wang, 2018). The key results of the Initial Coin Offerings study helped fuel insights to make stakeholders aware of what to watch out for in this space and whether this area would hold its weight over time or was it just another attempt to grab the cash and leave.

However, even though there were costs to this solution, there could be potential savings attributed to the platform. This result would want to be evaluated by the manufacturers and the users in the community. For instance, blockchain could potentially provide energy and financial infrastructure savings to ensure sustainable development and asset transfers to ensure efficiency and energy savings (Cocco et al., 2017). As a result, these cost savings could incentivize manufacturers to move from a more capital cost approach to these subscription-based models in a community-based model approach. This approach was not new, as blockchain has emerged with Bitcoin and its application as a decentralized system (Es-Samaali et al., 2017). As a result, while this technology was occurring, there was a lot of research showing this technology being used in these instances as a result of using these approaches. Additional analysis could be done to review the blockchain history and records to

check the source and addresses to understand further each transfer's intent and reflection attempt (Liu Xiao et al., 2021). In addition, although the primary function of ledgers was to store data, their capability could be further expanded to support rules and functions for complex algorithms, contracts, and abilities, such as those designed for NFTs and gameplay (Yao-Chieh et al., 2020).

Technological Advances on the Platform

The technical side of the platform was another consideration, or benefit, to the platform as a result of digital technological advancements. A blockchain was consistent with a distributed ledger, where distributed ledgers could provide new ways to offer decentralized databases for increased control and security for end-users and decrease power from a centralized authority (Kassem, 2019). The security enhancements inside the platform could further relate to the challenges composed of the system due to the technological capabilities. Inside the blockchain, it was generated by checking against critical criteria that must be met, good performance, sufficient energy, nonvolatile storage, and sufficient entropy (Kortesniemi, 2019).

This capability offered could also be provided where workspace storage off the blockchain could occur. The files could be shared with end-users and secured (Jin, 2019). The example workspaces, as a result, could further be reviewed, which would then further be examined as an advantage to the NFT ecosystem allowing a gaming metaverse system to be additionally built on top. Economy advancement and design are complex and require critical socioeconomic systems and algorithms to be considered built-up (Liu Xiao et al., 2021). As a result, blockchains could further define processes that disrupt areas, such as reshaping industries and pushing new products and mechanisms like metaverse and play to earn

technologies (Clohessy & Acton, 2019). The evaluation and decision of which technologies and frameworks work with each other depends on the technical capabilities and the modeling (Fremantle & Scott, 2017).

Implementation of the Blockchain Framework

As an example of the working system, a Smart City was similarly developed as part of a qualitative model. The smart city concept was to improve the life quality of a city by reusing inactive resources. The blockchain further established credibility and tamper resistance by providing intelligent contract organization to prevent and reduce risks as part of a Smart City methodology (Huang, 2021).

When developing a smart city, for example, intelligent city application components could also decentralize data through a blockchain to further verify and approve changes and allow them to propose changes and corrections accordingly (Rotună, 2019). These components suggested change as part of an adjustment to the processes that further accelerated an overall strategy and proved a working model of the methods. A smart city could adapt and grow to enhance these components further and expand upon critical demonstrated systems by working off the blockchain methodology and provide inherent value through using private contracts, basically NFTs. The practical implications of a blockchain network inside a universe such as this were the lack of transparency and decentralization (Clohessy & Acton, 2019). The blockchain framework further expanded upon the topologies. It was extensible, such as offering the ability to build the Internet of Medical Things as a gaming platform to build deep learning models (Wu et al., 2020). Scalability issues occurred as the number of nodes increases, representing a trade-off of this system's performance and substance (Khan et al., 2021). The purpose of the miners

was to ensure a fair and trusted environment in a decentralized area. Allowing them to process transactions at a fee gives incentives to process (Zamani & Giaglis, 2018). The affordance of variables further constrains the blockchain due to the capabilities of the framework provided by the miners (Rossi et al., 2019).

Authentication and Security

Authentication and session management were vital components when working across an NFT, metaverse, and blockchain system. Identifying and tracking a user and their session across the lifecycle was essential to the defined overall plan. As part of creating inherent value and having a particular outcome, identity could become lost or stolen and easily misplaced, especially in refugee situations, where digital identity and tracking could be accomplished to ensure greater traceability (Button, 2018).

Having traceable identities, for example, could further prove if someone is who they say they are and provide proven ability of ownership of a particular wallet containing NFTs—proving the concepts of a hierarchical identity layer and how these identity layers would overlap. For example, ensuring a user's proper identity could then inform the processes across a system to mention what the user owns and then, as part of those ownership, detail how they would interact with what the user could potentially hold from what the user acknowledges, what additional value could be further added as a result.

Policy-based templating could help lockdown to standards and better ensure negligence does not occur on the network due to malicious actors (Fang et al., 2021). Record keeping as part of NFTs was not included as the contracts are adjusted accordingly, and the document standards are too vague to address (Cornelius, 2021).

In addition to reviewing the authenticity of a connection, checks and balances must be input to ensure further established processes. When using a decentralized application (dApp), oracles could help provide a centralized source of truth from trusted third parties who then bring data to these unverified channels to help ensure the proper trust of the data (Caldarelli & Ellul, 2021). Oracles also have a significant responsibility in correctly executing contracts, guaranteeing the right information goes into the right places. Otherwise, they are responsible for triggering if attempts to put the wrong information into the wrong places result from an attempted attack or misconfiguration (Caldarelli & Ellul, 2021). This is where the Oracles could issue refunds and credits to offset these mistakes further. Without these checks, though, malicious users could mint and abuse the system to go around the procedures to do what was not intended.

Oracles were further set up to certify and be the authenticity of the data at a cost to the end-user (Gatteschi, 2018). While costing a minimal amount, these checks could be there for the greater good of the whole working part. Ensuring the transition of technologies and designing it properly must ensure they flow properly to prove further.

AI-based performance was also a check to ensure these applications post unique and constrained challenges. Reviewing the impact these have on users was essential, and vetting through the blockchain, this impact could be further investigated (Badsha et al., 2021; Islam et al., 2021). Digital technologies and improved connectivity are crucial to overcoming obstacles in industries where centralization has become the norm (Tanaka & Evans, 2020). Blockchains were often referred to as the primary innovation and potential to disrupt many industries. This was no different from the metaspaces universe and gaming platforms (Clohessy & Acton, 2019). The

lifecycle of the approaches were further reevaluated by reviewing the properties of a contract and then declaring what were needed to confirm these contracts on the chain (Governatori et al., 2018).

An IPFS system could also be reviewed as part of an interconnected system to further connect in a decentralized hosting viewing of images and assets across a blockchain approach (Karbasi & Shahpasand, 2020). The growing impact on the blockchain was further proof of the smart contracts and exploited capabilities that could be provided to provide algorithmic computations to further leverage and educate as part of ensuring a trusted and advanced platform (Ciatto et al., 2020)

NFT Centralization Risk & Mitigation Strategies

In a previous study by Kai Risius, intelligent contracts were pushed out using the Blockchain platform and proved the orchestration concepts of the systems working together (Risius, 2017). Specifically, blockchain-distributed ledgers were responsible for intelligent contracts and dynamic business functionality used during business transactions and processing on publicly available blockchains. In addition, making these immutable contracts further proved the complexity and requirements showing how the code could not be changed once deployed. Making various changes would require a re-deployment of the infrastructure resulting in a centralization risk due to the attempted attempt methodologies (Konashevych, 2020). This further proved to leverage these for NFTs, and ensuring the data can not be changed over time makes them stand as a piece of Artwork or collectible that could not be replicated or stolen as a result of these occurrences on the ledger running atop a decentralized system. Transactional patterns were also demonstrated as a result of the holdings and circumstances, which could be

further evaluated; as a result to see what may have happened in this (Liu Xiao et al., 2021). To help prevent Denial of Service attacks on the infrastructure, it is further impactful which had a decentralized distributed system to handle the load (Xu et al., 2018). Forecasting was essential to the concept, but it was also challenging, so as a result, it would need to be reviewed. By leaving proper forecasting models, investment strategies could be designed and revised to have a predicted Bitcoin return and were statistically more robust (Guerra et al., 2020).

In a permissionless environment, one must consider how this would impact the roles and rights of interacting between systems from on-chain and off-chain systems as a result of the hybrid approach of the metaverse. For example, with every NFT owner and buyer, how would that affect working with the digitized asset and interacting with the transaction hash across private and public chains (Cornelius, 2021). These permissionless systems need to be carefully planned and executed as reviewed, whereby blockchain systems in permissionless systems participate in anonymous systems as they develop with various identities and methods (Feng, 2018). The reason for this was that it could be challenging to interact with anonymous users and have those users interact with a trusted system across the identities, ensuring permissionless. Still, a controlled system, yet de-centralized, could provide a more accessible environment to secure, control, maintain, and further establish as an authoritative source over a 51% source. The low rate of blockchain adoption had been involved because of its lack of understanding and innovation in organizational studies (Rogers, 1995; Yu and Hang, 2010; Van de Weerd et al., 2016). IT innovation could be defined as applying a new IT by an organization, individual, or unit (Swanson, 2004). A solution that resolved the scalability and network store part of the blockchain platform further enhances the elasticity of serverless applications. It

could further expand beyond the single task approaches (Palaiokrassas et al., 2021).

Prototyping was a critical component of reviewing blockchains and contracts while ensuring the proper systems were set up and functional and meeting the defined requirements

(Weingärtner et al., 2021). A smart contract could provide appropriate mechanisms and timestamp ordering methodologies, for example, when comparing the contributions to the protocols. Smart contracts allowed for the most effortless conversion while security was lower and more functions favored it (Y. Wang et al., 2021).

A blockchain-based booking system was developed to model various processes and then offered those out over the EVM nodes to ensure better automatic model checking (Dong et al., 2020). Being a part of a cryptocurrency study that evaluated the sources and online communities behind the scenes helped establish further credibility and marketing due to these factors. One hundred twenty-eight participants have targeted a result of one study to review the impact of cryptocurrency on their daily environment (Dospinescu & Caramangiu, 2018).

Metaverse Vision

The metaverse brought their interconnections and dependencies as an overall intertwined system. This brought their challenges which had a public chain and intelligent contracts trying to be interconnected amongst each other to prove further what was possible and prevent users from executing calls from outside a particular path, for example, making API calls and looking for weaknesses within a specific direction (Prasad & Ramachandram, 2021).

The system should inform the worker nodes of what private contracts there were and have been deployed due to these new instances and then further define them in a protected and executed way. The settlement should only occur once the finalized calls have been

implemented due to the confirmations (Yuan et al., 2018). Within a metaverse concept, there would be a series of public connected blockchains, known as a governance token, helping manage the payment methods, along with a series of private interconnected systems controlling non-fungible passes resulting from the possible interactions within a gaming environment or even an NFT universe. Ensuring the NFTs could interact with one another and were self-aware ensures the contracts themselves could intertwine and continue to expand due to these additional flexibilities.

Having private arrangements that could further call each other and interact with each other would allow the metaverse components to intertwine and realize due to the connected systems. Ensuring these private and public approaches were realized, tested, and secured is critical to ensuring the success and outcome of the metaverse subsystems. Solving double-spend was crucial as this resolved issues with assets, money, and any corresponding data on the chain, which was a vital issue with past systems (Moiling et al., 2020). Blockchain technologies were further established for a specific purpose by ensuring they had machine learning mechanisms and were focused on the goal (Kamišalić et al., 2021). As one builds a metaverse, one must account for the economy, where the blockchain fits perfectly. More specifically, several initiatives had been advanced due to the popularity and rise of blockchain technology, allowing these applications to move real money across borders using blockchain technology, making it more accessible to the masses (Cocco et al., 2017). The vision of the metaverse also entailed implementing a real economy and basing it on a real-world system. In contrast, as a result, it could further expand across projects and tie multiple systems together

(Menghui et al., 2021). Bringing projects and plans together would further ensure a fortitude of options due to the partnerships and interconnectivity these areas could provide.

Another essential concept had a tradable economy as part of the universe. Evaluating trading where the markets are open 24x7, and it was necessary to note the differences and parallels resulting in cryptocurrency (Hudson & Urquhart, 2019). The overall processing power, especially with specialized equipment, could provide an extra hash rate to help power the underlying infrastructure needed to run the platform (Kim et al., 2020).

Data Interconnecting

When linking data on a blockchain to off-chain data, ensured unlinkability while maintaining linkability must be considered. For example, in a hospital and patient's privacy, how could medical data be stored on a blockchain but in a fashion to not link directly to an end-user. By figuring this concept out, one could further elaborate on expanding the art of the possible while ensuring the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act of 1996 and General Data Protection Regulation with a patient (Zhang et al., 2020). But if the data could be linked easily and identified, how does it get erased off a blockchain, or what would it look like (Zhang & Lin, 2018)? The blockchain system could be advantageous as it allows a distributed approach to storing health records and sharing them across stakeholders.

This opened up several questions about how this system could be restricted to specific entities and ensure only the proper patient access to the correct data at the right time. Encrypting this data and overcoming certain limitations would be the right way to protect and ensure protected data stays protected at the correct times during suitable events. Medical data

storage was proposed to claim privacy awareness with the exact location encryption to track the data across the platform (Yang, 2019).

Jung (2021) ensured this EMR data could be protected and accessed while staying encrypted, so bringing these concepts further into the metaverse space when resulting in players, characters, NFTs, and key data all encrypted as a result of critical contributions could further ensure non-immutability, reduced transparency, and necessary protections across the platform. Interoperability issues could occur due to two platforms, but open standards made connecting the two nodes easier via the Multiple CBDC bridge project (Jung, 2021). By interconnecting data, it was essential to ensure privacy as a result. Providing user data collected from a legal group was critical and happened with any of these systems and must stand up to compliance across the regions (Becher et al., 2020). Ensuring a permissionless structure is critical to the evolving needs of the application and framework. This builds off the decentralized approach, which allowed trust and verification to occur (Heo & Shin, 2021). Based time is essential due to immutability and authenticity (Ma et al., 2020). Reducing counterfeiting of digital items opens up possibilities with blockchain to write immutable transactions (Yiu, 2021).

In addition, to ensure data is on and off-chain, these processes must be integrated by enabling key cryptocurrency-related authenticated sources and further guaranteeing the computing resources were delegated (Kampik & Najjar, 2020). By integrating interconnected systems such as those that rely on cryptographic techniques, one could take advantage of a lower cost and overlay network to further expand the possibilities (Park et al., 2018). The blockchain voting system efficiently represents mismatches and determines which one would

win out (Xiaoyu Ma, 2020). Having traditional payment systems replaced by digital transactions made it easier to allow this to come to fruition due to the verifications (Hosseinian et al., 2020).

Media Attention

Increased cryptocurrency and global media attention could impact platform ecosystems due to increased or decreased cryptocurrency asset systems. The assets can be underlined and pressured due to outside influences, and these need to be considered for what the true capabilities could be handled in the future (Sarkintudu, 2019). With split revenue across markets, this opened the door for value increase and slippage across the ecosystem, allowing arbitrage and additional advantages that suit well in a metaverse and blockchain environment when dealing with in-game and out-of-game economies. Forming a monetary-based policy on a decentralized trusted platform could help accelerate and move forward the experiences where new standards could further be put into place for critical mass adoption.

Fake data could be further bolstered, and ensuring the proper leverage at the right time was essential (Reyes-Menendez et al., 2019). Providing a continuous play-to-earn concept can bring intriguing results to the economy as users were incentivized to gamify the system and further expand upon the elements and addictive nature. Then by winning NFTs and SFTs due to the performance, the influence shown in qualitative models would throw the addictive nature accordingly. The media spillover resulting from what was occurring was essential to understand the impact of the high-rank social media users and the overarching impact on the environment (Xie, 2019).

ERC-721

Standardizations in technology were not unusual. With NFTs, there was a standardization called ERC-721, which provides a baseline recommendation for developing a standardized NFT to interoperate across marketplaces on the Ethereum network. An Ethereum Request for Comments (ERC) was an application requesting blockchain standards (Muddasar & Bagui, 2021). ERC-721 was approved and moved to allow easy use, creation, and exchange of these digital assets on Ethereum. The standard provided for individual token ownership, required ten functions, and required three events tied to the contract. This specific standard had a unique offering that the NFT was non-fungible and unique. As described by (Valeonti et al., 2021), this standard was considered the goal standard among most token holders, collectors, and many other marketplaces, with the most critical fact that the digital asset could be unique when the creator develops the contract (Valeonti et al., 2021).

Gaps in the Literature

Research within the NFTs area was limited as of 2021 where there are limited perspectives on longer term use of NFTs and the impact of extending the use of these assets over-time. However, this was purely a trend where the estimated value of these NFTs of each purchase was in the millions as of 2021, becoming worthless in less than a year. As another example, the NFT hype has further been exaggerated when Twitter CEO Jack Dorsey sold the first Twitter message as an NFT for \$2.9 Million (Pinto-Gutiérrez et al., 2022). The Twitter message's value has declined to as low as \$280 as of April 2022 (Kauflin, 2022). Reviewing the concept of Smart NFTs would extend the life of these assets and provide extended utility and meaning to these digital assets without compromising value and raising value over time to these assets for as long they are utilized, thereby ensuring further utilization of the overall

platform. This was where the idea of the metaverse connected over multiplatform systems to bring the world and markets together to provide overall value to NFTs. For example, DEEPSPACE (\$DPS), a multiplayer blockchain-based open-world space-based strategy game created on the BNB Smart Chain (BSC), Axie Infinity (\$AXS), and others, had seen massive growth into the metaverse and play to earn space and have a combined market cap of over \$28 billion (Victor, 2021). DEEPSPACE leverages NFT tokens as a utility-based asset that can be uniquely upgraded over time with game-based attributes to enhance the characteristics further, thereby inherently increasing the value and uniqueness of the NFT.

Another example was digital art being created and sold for over \$69M, bringing ample media attention to this space and more focused from the outside, even though the tech itself has been around since the 1970s (Park et al., 2022). Digital assets research, specifically regarding utility NFTs, was missing today from what has been gathered because this was so new and was just being released; even Facebook was just coming out with the word Meta for a reason as a result of these new concepts. By reviewing the models out today and exploring the possibilities and consequences of real-life examples, one could further provide test cases of possible use cases of these scenarios due to these experiences on the open market. NFTs were continually being researched, and just whip-sawed in the 2022's demands, especially with the state of the crypto-winter markets going on, and yet the need for a utility NFT was being drowned out and ignored while poor choices were being made or ignored completely (Yang, 2022).

Conclusions

To conclude, one should continue to evaluate the effectiveness of play-to-earn tokens as a result of Smart NFTs and could see if the value of these NFTs is prolonged enough to justify the ends to their means compared to standard NFTs that were estimated to become worthless over time as a result of a frenzy that is occurring due to the meme trend that was happening as part of the era during this time. Digital assets were further needing to be researched as the gap in the literature clearly shows that consumers are making poor choices by not understating the value of NFTs and making quick decisions in the digital asset space today (Pinto-Gutiérrez et al., 2022). Identifying the types of NFTs out there, the standards for NFTs, and the kinds of NFTs, whether they contain a set of utilities or are meme NFTs, was a critical aspect of further clarifying the type of meme and further assigning a market value to the appropriate meme to help consumers understand an associated risk model the meme when making consumption choices on a project (Bamakan Seyed Mojtaba et al., 2022).

The metaverse further scales out the impact of the NFTs as these could be transferred into games and then provide in-game currency, making it even harder to assign a value and assess a clear score to the consumer with reputational value due to the volatility of such as assets. However, such assets could hold their value for longer as such games retain a user base for more extended periods of time.

Chapter Summary

Blockchain technologies had evolved a long way over the past decade. The critical platforms behind them were developing the digital currency system and industry as it expanded further into the various sectors. Smart contracts that the blockchain platform had opened the door to the metaverse opening new possibilities such as play-to-earn games and monetizing

non-fungible tokens or NFTs where value could be gained from digital assets (Goldston et al., 2022). Holding and retaining this value would be the challenge with creating something known as smart NFTs to add value further and use the assets over time to extend these creations over existence further. Ensuring continued utility and tokenization of these key concepts would ensure continued revenue, consumerization of critical values, and overall extended life to 2032 (Sandstrom, 2022). The chapter contained a literature review covering the research gaps, along with the media attention as part of the overall literature review. Next, the areas covered were authentication and security as part of the platform, along with a qualitative study of the general concept. Finally, decentralization risks were reviewed and summarized for their essential benefits (Yang, 2022). Now that the topics had been covered relating to the overall research, the next area would cover the Qualitative research components and the focused data insights provided as part of the research methods applied.

Chapter 3: Methodology, Design, and Methods

The purpose of this qualitative exploratory study was to determine how NFTs could be monetized and used by creating a market to provide the demand. This research study had examined this new space and to see how this could be reviewed to be developed into something useful. For example, NFTs could be used in a game world to connect users to in-game experiences, representing a metaverse interaction with NFTs or SFTs. The study opportunity was to investigate NFTs within the blockchain platform further to identify how adding utility and combining the utility inside a metaverse would hold the value of NFTs (Davis et al., 2009). Even the concept of loading NFTs inside the metaverse could arrive by big players allowing a more affordable and more accessible access option over time (Valeonti et al., 2021). Four hundred and ninety million dollars was the latest value the NFTs had generated in 2021 alone (Muddasar & Bagui, 2021). Artists wanted to use digital assets to sell art, but how was the value derived from the seemingly thousands of NFTs being minted at scale. The research would further be reviewed to identify ones with utility or provide extra weight on top of the art to see if those hold value over a more extended period. The intelligent contracts act like escrows and instead use oracles to provide a source of truth when interacting with the blockchain to confirm the digital asset (Ojog, 2021). The blockchain could further prove asset ownership, allowing for trading or other utility functions when interacting with the purchase.

An ERC-721 was a framework created for the Ethereum blockchain that says this type of token, the NFT, was unique and could have a different value from the same contract (Palmisano et al., 2022). Implementing a well-architected ERC-721 standard for NFT tokens could ensure consistency across the platform and data interoperability, allowing the digital assets to be

valuable and transactive on the platforms (Palmisano et al., 2022). The assets could be used for tickets, gaming, or digital art to establish a marketplace to further transact upon and communicate between a buyer and a seller to establish a relationship (Caldarelli, 2022). The economy involved could be further exploited depending on the buyer or seller, which could be leveraged depending on the asset's value going forward.

The research methodology defines the design used to address the study and opportunity as part of the research.

Research Methodology and Design

The qualitative research methodology selected for this study was part of what underpins this topic. The focus on qualitative methods would provide and generate new ideas for research and concepts while delivering critical determinations for providing definitive conclusions of addressing the question by giving an outcome (Ourzik, 2022). The planned approach was to gather qualitative survey responses from a community of crypto community users to gather additional insights on the NFT and metaverse and take this data in. The pragmatic approach focuses on a what works philosophy, where objectional approaches, such as natural and authentic approaches were processes that were integrated and were used (Everest, 2021). The reason the methodology was relevant was the approach focuses on the objectional process for this study, where just the facts are focused on, and no outside bias was brought in as part of the study.

The research design would be used was exploratory research (Marshall et al., 2013). Exploratory design was helpful in research that has not been covered in depth in the past and was fitting for the unique concepts covered from blockchain to metaverse research (Nandi et

al., 2021). A few case studies had been used to explore this area (Tomita et al., 2021). Still, an exploratory, dissertation-level, in-depth analysis had yet to be fully published in this space.

Several researchers were investigating the blockchain concepts within the cryptocurrency sector; for example, two articles in this space, such as Blockchain and smart contracts for insurance vectors, reviewed the vulnerabilities of Smart Contracts as a whole (Gatteschi, 2018; Prasad & Ramachandram, 2021). This would further help align the research in these verticals and align with the core concepts of these fields of study.

The target population would focus on crypto enthusiasts along with gamers. Some users could classify themselves as crypto games, but others could reflect as all-around individuals. This qualitative exploratory study aimed to determine how NFTs could be monetized and used by creating a market to provide the demand. With the criteria in mind, the goal for recruiting was to identify participants in the cryptocurrency space familiar with interacting with the blockchain, gaming, and NFT space to be able to interact with the platforms and not skew results accordingly (Zhang & Xiao, 2019). The study's sample size was around 50 users to get adequate qualitative survey data. The sample would be recruited from existing crypto and gaming communities. These communities had over 10k users, so finding 50 users willing to take a survey should not be a problem for this project. I would use Google Forms to collect the anonymous data. From there, data would be analyzed and coded to see the response trends using Google Forms and Google Sheets.

Population, Sample, and Participant Recruitment

As part of the study, the target population would be cryptocurrency platform users. Ensuring a familiar audience with blockchain technologies could impact how the technology is

adopted. The population was further focused on gaming enthusiasts who would know the platforms targeted as part of the metaverse. The overall criteria would match the purpose of determining how NFTs can be monetized and used by creating a market to provide the demand. In addition to these requirements, the participants must understand how to interact with the blockchain. They would be familiar with the social community so they can see the survey to participate. These were some of the basic requirements to join in and experience as part of the study. The estimated size of the target population was well over 10,000 community members.

The minimum study size would be 50 respondents for the survey. In a qualitative design process, increasing survey respondents were not necessarily better for data accuracy (Skinner et al., 2022). Similar studies using qualitative surveys have used responses of 100 or fewer (Han et al., 2022). A purposive sampling procedure of criterion sampling would be used. Study participants must meet the study criteria. The recruitment post would be posted on the community site. A collection of 50 surveys would gathered from the received responses as part of the data collection. As demonstrated by the researcher Marshall, having too many answers was not necessarily better because it could skew the results. Reviewing the data gathered and ensuring spam results. Accurate data results would be essential to ensure bot responses were weeded out due to the intelligence gathered. A set of criteria to ensure a competent, focused set of users as the participants needed a baseline set of knowledge to interact with the blockchain and connect with the game.

The survey participants would be recruited through crypto groups and gaming groups, providing enough focus to gather the results needed to obtain the necessary data to analyze the data. The cryptocurrency groups were focused on metaverse games and the areas with

previous experience interacting with the blockchain and this behind the scenes experience. The experience that had been obtained by the participants, removed the barrier to entering, thereby, created better research data than just by having research data that consists of unknowns. The expectation would be that most of the respondents would not respond but retain a big enough group that could theorize enough respondents to fulfill the requirements. Permission was already allowed because, in the cryptocurrency world, everything was anonymous anyways. I am already one of the founders and had received permission from the team. In addition, when users sign up, they provide their approval through the terms of use. Also, when the recruitment post and Google Form were posted, they would agree to the terms of use on the Form when filling out the form, which would be posted on the community Discord site.

Data Collection Instrumentation and Procedures

The data collection tool used for this study was a survey. Specifically, a Google Form with detailed questions regarding the concepts of the metaverse activities relevant to the study purpose would be used. Providing detailed questions would ensure a complete response on the core concepts of what to look for and how to evaluate them. The survey questions were presented in Appendix A. Questions would focus on critical technical insights with critical topics of blockchain, cryptocurrency, metaverse, and NFTs. The key reason to use surveys was to help gather participants feeling, experiences, and trust within a decentralized platform and understanding of bringing the forum into gaming (Taherdoost, 2022). It also helped the individuals feel like their voices were heard, and continuous improvements were made due to the changes and potential concepts being addressed going forward.

To start with the data collection technique, a Google Form would be issued to the community and offered to anyone willing to participate. A sampling of 50 participants would be gathered and used through the process of valid data to take the responses and analyze them for further scrutiny. As part of the data collection, ensuring accurate data such as complete and accurate responses, informed consent, and reflective responses would be guaranteed to capture the intent of the outcomes as opposed to blindness input. Recruitment was inferred of users as the community that was brought in has been pre-screened as having crypto accounts, social media with registered access to NFTs, and experience utilizing NFTs with a gaming approach.

Finally, data would be stored with Google Cloud as part of the Google Sheets, where Google Forms stores the data and would be retained for up to seven years as part of the agreement with Google. Potential participants interested in the study would follow the link to the survey provided in the recruitment post. Before answering any survey questions, participants must voluntarily agree to the informed consent statement supplied as the first question on the Google Form. As part of the survey collections, age range and wallet address would be collected, which was anonymous and harder to track. As the participants worked through the survey, they would be required to provide short answers to each survey question. Otherwise, the survey would be terminated due to a timeout function. Each question was marked as required within the survey so a participant could not continue on to the next question until the previous one had been answered. Once the survey had been completed, the participant would be finished participating in the study. The survey was estimated to take a maximum of 10 minutes to complete. No personal identification information would be

collected in this process. Survey responses would be downloaded and transferred to Google Forms for analysis. Safe storage would help ensure data integrity within Google Cloud.

Before beginning the study, a pilot study would be conducted. The pilot study's purpose was to determine and understand the optimal number of participants that would be used in the pilot study. The pilot study would further help to ensure the randomization techniques. These pilot study participants would meet the study criteria, but the data obtained from their responses would not be included in the study findings. Selecting the proper standards and determining the correct focus audience would help ensure the proper outcome and results within the final study.

Permission for use would be asked for during the Google Form and was also granted as part of being on the project and in terms of use. The cryptocurrency community was entirely anonymous, so users were always more open to presenting information because nothing easily correlated back to an individual participant.

Data Analysis and Procedures

When collecting and looking through the data associated with the surveys, themes would be considered, such as consistent messaging around NFTs as a utility or messages they go against this statement and tracking the respondents to where they are leaning towards one or the other indecisive. As part of the codebooks developed and themes, these would be used to provide relevant data and results to understand better the results' accuracy and the answer to the overall research question (Conrad & Tucker, 2019). Card sorting could be further used to help identify this data, distill the results, and look into the overarching answer to the question to understand if the respondents provided enough insights to bring relevant data forward.

Utilizing Google Sheets would allow for scaling through the data looking for trends in the criteria of the collected data. Examples of the collected data would be looking at the demographics, sorting through the demographic ranges, and correlating that with the experienced users in NFT holders. Identifying any trends or comparisons with the data would find compelling results to determine answers to the questions asked around what the participants consider a value NFT and point to the original thought of the study.

There were many approaches to collecting data to analyze the data further to determine the final results and impact of the research. Google Forms, with the use of Google Sheets, would be the tool to help decipher the data. As part of reviewing the data, some of the themes would be reviewed for using an NFT with utility over a meme NFT. Another consideration would be the quality of the NFT, such as capabilities provided by an NFT, for example, an upgrade NFT versus a static one. Another capability of an NFT that would be evaluated as part of the data collection would be to see the utility of an NFT, such as the perks, versus one that did not have access to such perks or resources. While there are many options of digital assets to choose from, having a utility NFT would it make a difference in interacting with a metaverse or would not adjust the value, and the data collected through the survey would highlight the appropriate data to help circle back to the initial question highlighted in the study.

Trustworthiness

Trust involves expectations and motives or the willingness to act. The main focus was trusting the results as a reader and ensuring one could authorize the study results and findings. By building the evidence and providing the accuracy of the research, one could guarantee the conclusions were relevant, accurate, and overall trustworthy (Zhou & Miguel Baptista, 2013).

Trustworthiness was ultimately a single point of failure, and without it could lead to insufficient data and a collapse in the case. Working through it and providing safeguards or risk mitigation strategies to letting the participants trust the researcher as much as possible is the best way to ensure trust. Building trustworthiness as part of the survey approach was critical to getting participants to understand and provide essential data as part of the study. If the participant does not trust the survey, the data would be inaccurate (Salminen et al., 2022). It was also essential the study would consist of credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability. All of which the examination must demonstrate, or it could undermine the fundamental research.

Credibility was the focus on where the research builds the believability and convincing or background trustworthiness of the reputation of the researcher and participants (Jeng & He, 2022). For example, providing a depth of research and resources in the dissertation demonstrates the knowledge the researcher had acquired, putting the information together to understand where they were at. Additional credibility was inferred as part of the study with the non-random purposive sampling approach. When one takes a purposive sample, the bias was reduced through the criteria met by the research participants, which could build the verifiability and credibility within the findings and build the outcomes as a more critical use case and additional findings. The data collected would be totaled together for each outcome and brought together in different perspectives to determine the outcomes and predictions.

Throughout the project, credibility would be preserved by referencing and using quality sources and critical focus points when bringing in research areas. The transferability was achieved by providing the mechanisms and replicating how this data was gathered throughout

the research study to allow others to mimic the results. Building a shared understanding of the knowledge, trust, reputation, and surrounding concepts within the beliefs and assumptions defined could further build mutual ground on the social roles and ideas used throughout the research (Xie et al., 2022). Finally, confirmability was further engrained by demonstrating the results effectively throughout the investigation. Replicating the results within others' research could further build upon the research to identify the knowledge share between researchers as part of the studies (Underhill, 1995). To establish dependability, Google Forms was provided in Appendix A to highlight other survey questions. Trust also related closely to the idea of reliability in the research view. Having dependable research was also reliable, ensuring it could consistently be accurate, precise, and trustworthy (Bashir et al., 2008). Properly providing proper analysis was critical to have the right results at the right time.

Confirmability was also established by testing the questions, ensuring the results and data were connected correctly and showing personal data staying out of the system. The methods were linked and further influenced as a result. Providing certainty and results was essential to the validity of the results as a way to triple-check the outcome to avoid mistakes, bias, and misinterpretations of the data and findings. Determining an expected outcome, then providing a specific metric to the development could ensure a repeatable process for re-affirming and providing process rigor to the functions and providing dependable results to the continuity of the research provided by the study.

Ethical Assurances

Study processes would be put into place to better ensure the ethical standards were abided by and the participants' identities were protected by aggregating the data and ensuring

the anonymized data could not be tracked back to the participants. This would also ensure the data was better trusted and the participants provided better information because they understood it was anonymized. As part of the Belmont process, that would be followed was respect for each survey taker by ensuring their privacy, informed consent of their privacy, and storage of their data for the seven years via Google. The data would be anonymized by not asking for their email and not requesting any Google email (Dutka & Astroth, 2022). There were no potential risks to the candidates taking the surveys as no personal information or threat of secrets are being asked due to this survey. In addition, there were no direct benefits to carrying out this survey either. The recruitment would be a straightforward process where users in the online community would be messaged a Google Form for participation.

The benefits to society were to provide further awareness of the value of NFTs and understanding of what an NFT was, its potential of perceived value, and how one could further value it in a different light, more than just an image. Still, underlying stats or behind-the-scenes technicalities as opposed to just reviewing its face value. Understanding all aspects of an NFT and the benefits from all sides, one could make a better-informed decision before getting an NFT from a marketplace. The more considerable benefit to society was by further expanding on the research in the field and focusing on the new NFT area that had been picking up attention.

Chapter Summary

The research provided demonstrated the overall recruitment of study participants, data gathered, and the data collection processed and procured. The comprehensive data collection and instrumentation process were further discussed within the areas. The themes and insights covered the expectations and data focal points as part of asking the survey responders to

provide detailed answers or quick summaries to the questions and additional information to protect the aspects of the research question from analyzing further what was covered and what was not. These aspects helped to build credibility for the general research topic. In addition, the trustworthiness and ethical assurance were further evaluated as part of the research study to demonstrate the results from the findings of the focus area in the project. As part of Chapter 4, the survey process would be reviewed to highlight the results and conclusions. Results would reveal more insights into the research process to see the narratives and survey responses to those areas.

Chapter 4: Findings

The purpose of this qualitative exploratory study was to investigate how NFTs can be monetized and used by creating a market to provide the demand. This research study examined this new space and explored how this could be developed into something useful. The study opportunity was to investigate NFTs within the blockchain platform further to identify how adding utility and combining the utility inside a metaverse would hold the value of NFTs (Davis et al., 2009). The concept of loading NFTs inside the metaverse could arrive by big players allowing a more affordable and accessible access option over-time (Valeonti et al., 2021). Four hundred and ninety million dollars was the latest value the NFTs generated in 2021 alone (Muddasar & Bagui, 2021). Artists want to use digital assets to sell art, but how would the value be derived from the thousands of NFTs being minted at scale? The intelligent contracts act like escrows and use oracles to provide a source of truth when interacting with the blockchain to confirm the digital asset (Ojog, 2021). The blockchain could further prove asset ownership, allowing for trading or other utility functions when interacting with the purchase. The data collection has been completed from the survey captured as part of the study, and the analysis will be provided for the critical insights from the data collected.

In this chapter, the study findings that will be presented will tie back to the central research questions and the study's overall purpose. Investigating the key themes within the following sections will demonstrate the overall results of the questions and conclude.

Description of the Study Sample

The study sample size was 44 respondents as part of the qualitative survey. The target population consisted of users on a cryptocurrency platform. As an additional datapoint,

identifying how the blockchain could be adopted was also analyzed and detailed. An extra measure followed was to provide a familiar audience with how blockchain technologies could affect how technology is adopted and used. The population was further focused on gaming enthusiasts who would know the platforms targeted as part of the metaverse. In addition to these requirements, the participants needed to understand how to interact with the blockchain technologies to understand better using the platform and concepts. They were also familiar with the social community, so they could see the survey to participate in—a purposive sampling method was used for this study. The written text acquired from survey responses consisted of multiple choice responses and some fill-in-the-blank responses to provide data that informed the research questions. Google Forms collected the reactions, and Google Forms also stored the data in Google Sheets.

As part of this study, the attributes and characteristics are essential concepts. For example, looking at the participant's age and experience with NFTs, the median range of 20 – 45 appear to have the most experience interacting with NFTs. In contrast, the outside age ranges have notably less experience. The data shown in Figure 2 reflect the background experience demonstrated by the participants, which influences the remainder of the case study given this background. The participants were engaged in various cryptocurrency groups as part of triaging and requesting involvement.

Figure 2

Comparing Experience Interacting with NFTs and Participant's Age.

Results

As part of the results the overall themes that were identified revolve around three central themes. The themes were market creation, utility effectiveness, and unique characterizations, all containing a subset of topics and details as part of the data points identified throughout this section. The sub themes from within the market creation review how markets could be determined around an investors potential or interest in a particular market and those could be captured as a result of key components whether its influence of timing or an understanding of branding or awareness. Another topic that was further explored was utility effectiveness where the more an NFT value that could be perceived as a result of the access and benefits the more an investor would potentially want to hold and for the longer

period or duration of time. Finally, the unique characterizations were further influenced where the concepts of limited amounts of NFTs and also the key attributes that make the NFT desirable were reviewed.

The survey was conducted to demonstrate a perspective of the metaverse and NFTs that present the thoughts and views of the studied area. Complete survey results are shown in Appendix B. In terms of understanding why individuals are obtaining NFTs, the highest accounted response for the category of the NFT is the future utility, which drives most folks to get the NFTs initially. As part of this observation, another insight provided by data is that while the most popular type of NFT is a utility form of the NFT, those same participants also commented on not selling the NFT or, in other words, holding. Throughout the survey, participants were asked how they interacted with NFTs in the metaverse for gaming. One participant noted, “the utility [of an NFT] is important. If the NFT gives me a chance to, for example, play a game to develop it”. Covering the environment and having a tangible use for NFTs were among the popular opinions. More specifically, another participant directly commented, “Like it more because the NFT would have more utility.” In addition, the findings also demonstrated the concept of long-term utility as a driver to hold and maintain ownership of the assets as a result of the direct use or utility of the assets, as noted by a third participant.

A survey respondent noted, for instance, “Non-hypothetical: Created NFTs as exclusive means of accessing product with demand,” whereas utilizing an NFT to access a resource is intriguing and essential as a concept to acquire an NFT. This aligns with the ideas of previous NFT collections mentioned within this study, such as the Bored Ape Yacht Club, where the

reasons to acquire these NFTs were to develop exclusive access and rights as part of holding the NFT.

A question that was brought up to the participants was about the type of NFTs and which ones were most important to them. The most common response was Metaverse Gaming NFTs, contributing to acquiring NFTs (36 out of 44). By establishing this clear criterion, the projections of quality projects over others could be more easily determined and scoped.

The floor price was also an essential factor in an overall NFT collection. More specifically, a survey respondent mentioned, "Make a clear distinction between the best and the worst. In any NFT project, even the worst ones increase in value if the best ones are super expensive." In this aspect, the floor price could be heavily weighted by each of the NFTs within the collection. As commented, the more expensive the NFT, the higher the transaction, and the higher the floor price that would be weighted against the collection's overall value.

For example, as the survey demonstrated, more than half the survey respondents found that ownership and uniqueness are among the essential characteristics for obtaining an NFT (27 of 44). To characterize the data, one respondent specifically responded, "Prefer holding in digital wallet cause I am not capable of that actions (dummy in that technology)," inferring that the ownership of the wallet and ease of use with wallet tools could provide an easier way to acquire and hold an NFT in a digital wallet and would more likely lead to an investor acquiring one.

Ensuring someone feels like they own an asset that cannot be taken away from an individual provided one of the highest characteristics for holding NFTs. In addition, the fact that the NFT is not a duplicate of others that exist in the world and is unique played an essential role

in the consumers' mindset regarding selecting an NFT. One participant specifically stated when considering creating an NFT collection; one would want to "Create a limited collection, [with] good marketing with important influencers from around the world, prizes, make the NFTs have something special that no other NFTs have." In addition, there are two characteristics. The first characteristic is ownership of the asset, which is an essential part of the value structure outlined by the participant. The second characteristic is the uniqueness of the NFT or uniqueness of the NFT and ensuring there are enough differences between each NFT within a collection for each one to be desirable.

Scouting to identify pre-lists, or just by wanting to obtain multiple items from an NFT collection, known in the community as "ape in," was sourced from friends or being a part of trading groups. This information was another common way to be a part of the in-the-know. Sometimes these lists provide just the ability to get into a mint, other times they were discounted or even free mints. Half of the respondents indicated that their friends were the referral source for obtaining one or more NFTs of a particular collection (24 of 44). One of the essential aspects of identifying whether an individual wants to participate in a pre-minting is the transparency and legitimacy of the project. As commented by a participant, "Novelty of the project, doxxed team, roadmap, previous projects of the team/company, social impact (if charity-related)," where these items were all specifically related to reasons to want to be involved in a pre-listing or wishing to participate. Transparency was one of the most commonly selected items; as another example by another participant, "security and transparency of the launch" were also key points. As cryptocurrency events demonstrate, one can't have trust without building trust.

The additional question was, “What sources do you consider reliable when acquiring an NFT?”. The responses mainly ranged toward “Friends.” However, there were also a few other surprise responses too, such as “Celebrity Endorsements” or “Influencers” and then also “Media Publications.” One additional response that seemed to pop-up as a commonality for the referenced question was also a security audit and whitepaper which is also enjoyable. In cryptocurrency, a security audit by a known and reputable firm is becoming increasingly recommended to have that stamp of approval or once review on your asset to get a further nod of trust in the cryptocurrency space.

When reviewing NFT projects just starting up, one question posed to the participants was, “Hypothetically, if you are the project creator of an NFT, what are some tasks you would do to create demand?” It was not surprising that most of the respondents did not expressly state the same response; they basically said the same idea or concept. They all hinted at marketing. Some participants directly stated marketing, while others noted a “strong community.” In the cryptocurrency space having a community is the same effect as advertising or marketing. This is key to a living and breathing project is the way that marketing occurs. There were also a ton of variable responses that would also be useful for further research in the future that some of them tied into the metaverse properties such as VR or other areas such as “Proof of Insurance,” which could be an interesting future project for a whole different research sector. Still, overall there was a majority difference in responses, with many other concepts brought up in this section for discussion.

A critical question that was also asked and is essential from the start for NFT or even token assets was considering the blockchain on which a project will run. Participants responded

that Ethereum was the overall chain used, with many stating Polygon and Binance as other chains. The data was not surprising as Ethereum, as of 2022, is the heavy NFT chain used for most projects leveraging the most common platform OpenSea. In addition, as part of the survey results, OpenSea was the most responsive to the medium used for NFT trading across all the participants. The leveraged blockchain can make or break a project, as this is where the investors are, and not having an accessible platform or chain would result in little to no traction.

Discussion of Study Findings

Understanding the current results as part of the qualitative results demonstrated that the data provided, while subjective, is also telling as part of building credibility, considering the sampling and the sample size taken as a result of the data. One speaking area of the data was the majority of the responses contained the request for focusing on Utility NFTs as a critical characteristic of obtaining an NFT (31 of 44). As an example of a comment on a utility NFT collection, one of the participants commented, “The NFT market was looking for utility in the crypto world and the normal world, in the case of games a useful, friendly way to use the NFTs example DEEPSPACE game. Anyone could use an NFT in DEEPSPACE and give it utility in the game.” The DEEPSPACE (DPS) collection was known for its unique utility attributes and dynamic contract capabilities to allow NFTs to evolve and expand over time.

Throughout the study, additional insights were determined; for example, the marketplace options proved that regardless of where the NFTs are acquired from or what chain is used, as long as the consumer knew about the NFT and it fits their interests, the consumer would receive it. One participant provided great insight, “If the market is volatile, sure, I'll sell

for profit or stake it, but otherwise, I believe in the long-term utility and holding it can be a real game-changer.” This also tied to another concept when the markets get rough; the common perception was to hold the NFTs rather than trying to sell them at a loss or minimal profit. There have been studies performed on market analysis. For example, in the Chinese stock market, it has been shown low or no information released and bearish markets being formed can affect stock market crashes in China (Chu et al., 2021). Evaluating and reflecting on these cryptocurrency markets that tie closer to the stock markets have many of the same perspectives. The information gathered from the survey demonstrated investors attempt to hold as a result as long as there is “transparency and legitimacy.” Similar to public stock markets, it was even more expected in cryptocurrency to have information disclosed as part of the projects. It was an exciting find that confirms this thought as part of reviewing the overall data as part of this study.

The detailed survey results have been included in Appendix B, where additional data has been sorted and included further to understand the respondents’ viewpoints on cryptocurrency. Including the data helps present a transparent and credible perspective, whereas in many studies, this was not included; it leaves the audience with a lack of understanding of the conclusions reached (Tomita et al., 2021). As part of overcoming these challenges in identifying the data structure, as provided earlier, the data results could help build the integrity of the study and allow for future research to be conducted on the included data.

The research question addressed from the survey questions was, how can NFTs be monetized and used by creating a market to provide the demand? This research question was divided into two sub-questions to help classify and categorize the concepts. The first sub-

question was, as markets mature, could comparable NFTs be evaluated to determine the effectiveness of utility NFTs? The surveys highlighted that the “long-term utility” of the project was most important. At the same time, the “potential for profit” arrived second for the selection and comparison of NFTs across the market. The survey data demonstrated that NFTs could be monetized and used to create a need and provide the demand. As shown by the detailed research results in Appendix B, making NFTs with characterizations, whether existing or new, could inherently create or add on to an existing market and thereby create the demand to drive investors to the NFTs.

The second sub-question that was also reviewed was what unique characterizations and market conditions are required. Based on the results, the survey participants highlighted that as market conditions matured, their opinions would mostly not change in the reports of the NFTs that would be invested in (17 of 44). Specifically, as one individual called out, “NFTs and good project show value in time, regardless of market conditions, but of course, when the market matures, it can only benefit and not make it less valuable.” The results were the same when the market deteriorated, and the overwhelming response was that no design would change (26 of 44). The results aligned with the perspective that NFTs appear not to follow what a traditional asset would follow. Instead, the consumer interest in acquiring and holding onto them would fall back to the overarching idea that the characterizations and project itself were more important than the market conditions. Based on the findings, NFTs could create new markets and entice demand by relying on unique and limited characteristics defined throughout this research.

Chapter Summary

The findings demonstrated a sampling of the cryptocurrency market speculation about NFTs. Reviewing the data from the survey shows how NFTs and the metaverse are viewed today. As a result, these perceptions could influence the global markets when applied holistically, at scale. The findings further demonstrated the conclusion to the research questions, identifying how the needs of the market are not only independent of the characteristics of an NFT but, furthermore, the more influence a project had on, and the greater the utility an NFT has was one of the biggest drivers to investing in an NFT. In Chapter 5, the discussion of the concluding results will be analyzed as the final part of the study.

Chapter 5: Discussion and Conclusions

The purpose of this qualitative exploratory study was to investigate how NFTs can be monetized and used by creating a market to provide the demand. This research study examined this new space and saw how this could be reviewed to be developed into something useful. For example, NFTs can be used in a game world to connect users to in-game experiences, which represents a metaverse interaction with NFTs or SFTs. A qualitative research approach was used to understand the characteristics of the social phenomena on why NFTs may or may not be more valuable as a utility in a metaverse environment as a utility (Liu et al., 2020). The study opportunity is to investigate NFTs within the blockchain platform further to identify how adding utility and combining the utility inside a metaverse would hold the value of NFTs (Davis et al., 2009). Even the concept of loading NFTs inside the metaverse could arrive by big players allowing a more affordable and accessible access option over time (Valeonti et al., 2021). Four hundred and ninety million dollars is the latest value the NFTs have generated in 2021 alone (Muddasar & Bagui, 2021). Artists want to use digital assets to sell art, but how is the value derived from the seemingly thousands of NFTs being minted at scale. The research will further be reviewed to identify ones with utility or provide extra weight on top of the art to see if those hold value over a more extended period.

An ERC-721 is a framework created by Ethereum that says this type of token, the NFT, is Unique and can have a different value from the same contract (Palmisano et al., 2022). Implementing a well-architected ERC-721 standard for NFT tokens can ensure consistency across the platform and data interoperability, allowing the digital assets to be valuable and transactive on the platforms (Palmisano et al., 2022). The assets can be used for tickets,

gaming, or digital art to establish a marketplace to further transact upon and communicate between a buyer and a seller to establish a relationship (Caldarelli, 2022). The economy involved can be further exploited depending on the buyer or seller, which can be leveraged depending on the asset's value going forward.

Limitations of Study Findings

The target elements within this research space covered NFTs and the metaverse as a utility on the blockchain. The scope further focused on the utility in this fashion and how it could interact with marketing, gaming, and the economic impact of the interoperability of these components.

The limitations of this study were focused on not going beyond the mentioned boundaries and, as such, would disregard other types of NFTs outside the ERC-721 standard and not on the standard OpenSea trading platform. By ensuring a consistent trading platform that is analyzed and reviewed, these boundaries could be further limited to a focused research topic. Going to non-standards or new standards and off-marketplaces can skew the results and provide too many variables that would skew the results of the NFT values, which would further result in ineffective data and inaccurate results in the research process. In the blockchain, anyone can create a contract, whether it follows a standard or not, as long as it follows the correct code for the particular blockchain. As long as the marketplace, or a custom marketplace, is created to read the blockchain and present the data, the digital assets could be displayed to the end-users. Following the standards makes it easier for transferability and interoperability across digital wallets and standardized tools and marketplaces, as those are more likely to be able to display and work with end-users.

There were a few sampling challenges with this study in terms of recruitment. For example, the sampling was done in cryptocurrency eccentric groups pre-exposed to NFTs, cryptocurrency, and gaming backgrounds, which may have some influence or predisposition over bias. The justification for this area is that the participants would also have the education needed to understand the market and the impacted scope to understand the asked survey questions. A general audience would not be able to respond without having a background in this area.

The limitations provided further reinforce the study, which helps provide additional perspective and value due to the data collected from the audience. The participants responded with their views based on the criteria and their understandings of the market value, which further reinforced the market concepts for what was necessary at the time of impact and current trends, adding more weight and credibility to current conditions, which further removed bias in the data from any of the potential researcher's influence.

Interpretation of Study Findings

NFT markets have been inherently ripe for new markets due to the ability to identify needed characteristics, utility, and different perspectives for what investors are looking for to determine demand. Monetizing the markets could occur as a result of aligning to market perspectives. In the upcoming section, the market creation and monetization areas have been further reviewed to understand how these have occurred. The findings from the study impact these data points.

Monetization and Market Creation

The research findings further reviewed the overarching research questions for the study. The first main question was, how could NFTs be monetized and used by creating a market to provide the demand? The research findings determined that NFTs can be monetized and used to create a market and provide the demand. As demonstrated by the detailed research results in Appendix B, creating NFTs with characterizations, whether existing or new, can inherently create or add on to an existing market and thereby create the demand to drive investors to the NFTs. In addition, the results aligned from this perspective as this is telling for where NFTs, as of this study, appear not to follow what a traditional asset would follow but instead, the consumer interest in acquiring and holding onto them would purely fall back to the overarching idea that the characterizations and project itself is more important than the market conditions.

The determination and effectiveness of a utility of an NFT was another key finding that determined the effect a particular asset could have on a market when released. As part of the next findings, the scope of the importance of utility was reviewed to better understand the relationship and importance of the balance of the attribute for the release of the NFT collection to the market.

Utility Effectiveness

The first sub-question reviewed in the study was, as markets mature, could comparable NFTs be evaluated to determine the effectiveness of utility NFTs? Based on the findings, NFTs can be used to create new markets and entice demand by relying on unique and limited characteristics defined throughout this research. Even as markets pull back due to a market downturn, markets are still being created and bet on in riskier assets, such as NFTs, able to

create volume and demand due to the perceived value of newer collections. The idea of holding an NFT for its long-term value or flipping an NFT in a trading market can vary depending on the investor's goals. However, overall, the market pressures of buying and selling are still perceived when the proper advertising, influencing, and uniqueness is brought into perspective. In addition, the study demonstrates an NFT anywhere cannot just occur but rather a focused blockchain with active investors and an active market. Ethereum is the biggest market as of 2022, where most of the trading volume appears on OpenSea on that particular chain. While supported, other chains, such as BNB Smart Chain, have significantly less book due to adoption and investor support.

The final set of outcomes as part of the findings was identifying the unique characterizations and specific market conditions the NFT collections would have on a market. The more unique and limited an NFT collection was, the better it performed regardless of conditions, and what would be reviewed in the next section would reveal the detailed data points for the characteristics of these areas.

Unique Characterizations and Market Conditions

The second sub-question that was reviewed was what unique characterizations and market conditions would be required? As demonstrated by the Twitter example, where former CEO Jack Dorsey sold the first Twitter message as an NFT for \$2.9 Million (Pinto-Gutiérrez et al., 2022), an NFT of perceived value or art can influence the market or create demand because of its perceived value which as a result which then had the draw. This value further deteriorated as of April 2022, where the highest bid offered was \$280, over a 99% decline (Kauflin, 2022). This coincided with what participants stated regarding usage and art or historical events that

are important in building a market or demand to create supply or uniqueness, which drives value. The study research questions help further address a question related to a practice-oriented problem in the field of computer science by diving into the more profound questions of the newly created area in the field of the blockchain and, more specifically, NFTs that sit on top of the blockchain. To address the study purpose, primary and sub-research questions were developed.

The data collected also demonstrated, as another example, where utility tokens, such as the DEEPSPACE example, were of significant value or in high demand to participants asking that they wanted to be able to use the assets for something of value rather than hold and hope the value of the assets would gain over time as a meme or piece of art (12 of 44). Having a utility or inherent value over time by adding to the intrinsic usefulness over time, such as leveling up the attributes of the token by using the asset in the game over time, would increase the value of the asset over time and thereby increase the worthiness of the attribute and proved this out in the data collected.

Practice Implications of Study Findings

The problem that was addressed was how the gaming community and metaverse could tie in a player's opportunity and tie NFTs to a 3D game environment and provide utility, thereby enticing to create a market around a collection. Getting a player's attention and encouraging a player to participate as part of the community by providing a sense of purpose or belonging is critical to a game's success and will help add value to the overall project. As demonstrated by the survey findings, participants responded that a substantial undertaking, and a sense of inclusion, would more likely entice the longer hold times of wanting to participate and

encourage the participation of a project due to inclusion. In addition, the interoperability between NFTs has the ability to allow for further engagement across the gaming space with the use of NFTs being used across games. For example, one game company could utilize an NFT of a character which could then be extended into another game by another publisher, thereby extending its value. This not only solves the problem of creating demand for a particular NFT project but also creates an entirely new market which allows for a longer-term mindset and content creation due to the latest entries within this market.

In the computer science field, the results could be further used to combine AI and the ability to generate art utilizing machine learning and procedural generation concepts. The ability to produce and streamline visually stimulating artwork and quickly make enticing 3D artwork that is unique can help build collections that create demand at a cheaper and more significant scale in a shorter amount of time. Artblock platform showcases many of these art masterpieces that are generatively made as a result of AI creative processes and has begun to increase in demand in 2022.

Pharmaceutical industries are also impacted by 100,000 deaths annually and over \$200 billion of loss in the pharmaceutical industry with counterfeit drugs (Chiacchio et al., 2022). Legal requirements now require tracking the entire drug development lifecycle from manufacturing to distribution. As part of this serialization lifecycle, blockchain and NFTs can be used to develop a solution to track and identify the entire process.

Researcher Reflections

As a researcher with knowledge in the NFT and cryptocurrency space, I had an understanding of the markets and an expectation that one could create value based on a need

and demand. However, as I researched this area deeper, I did not realize the extent that this was true. For example, my understanding was only utility NFTs would work in this model, and demand would build due to this particular value. However, due to the data produced, almost any characteristic an NFT demonstrates can generate value and order. Specifically, as one individual called out, “NFTs and good project show value in time, regardless of market conditions, but of course, when the market matures, it can only benefit and not make it less valuable.” The results were the same when the market deteriorated, and the overwhelming response was that no design would change (26 of 44). Finding a relevant factor, whether historically related, music-related, meme-related, utility-related, gaming related, etc., could impact weight and build a market and demand.

Reviewing various NFTs models over the past few years has shown all sorts of characteristics that have been attempted to capture this emerging area over the years. Identifying the new trends and keeping up with the creative methods for generating new collections was like finding a diamond in the rough. Sometimes it is finding who you know and identifying a trend; other times, it defies logic. For example, the NFT space is extremely high risk and one concept to watch out for is the concept of a rug pull. A rug pull is where a project creator runs off with the investor's money leaving the investors high and dry (Valeonti et al., 2021). While one could look for high-risk projects, it is tough to look for collections like these because of how new everything was at the time of the study. There were no past projects to help build analytics or predictable signs of a potential rug pull. One could look at the deployer address or other blockchain analytics to decipher who the creator was and other analytics. Still, many collections are just a guessing game and word of mouth today while also looking at

different characteristics and their marketability. An example of a rug pull that occurred in 2022 was the Frosties NFT collection which generated \$1.5M, and the creators failed to provide the benefits advertised and instead rug-pulled the investors (Justic, 2022). The NFT collections further prove that one could create a market with benefits; it was also essential to execute this.

Recommendations for Further Research

Recommendations for additional research had also been presented in the additional areas that provide expanded perspectives on extending the study. The characteristics and criteria for the blockchain analysis tools could further be provided to expand for the verifiable identity to prove further you are who you say you are in a decentralized way across disparate solutions.

Recommendation 1

With the research data, the study could be further expanded into additional criteria for further study on blockchain analysis and other sectors from different characteristics to other chains, all of which lead to additional markets. One example of an additional market that could be evaluated as a unique characteristic would be using an NFT as a verifiable identity and assessing how this would work going forward (Jagger & Abu-Mahfouz, 2022). The Connect2NFT web shows how NFT holders' control could show how variable credentials could further expand the need to decentralize the condition of assets further and additionally utilize these NFTs as a way to control the user's identity in a decentralized manner with the holder owning their identity as an NFT along the entire control. Utilizing this methodology, one could look into a qualitative analysis that collects data from research participants reviewing the decentralized models that would further analyze how connecting to the models and assets impacts these

areas and using what was ordered. By combing what was collected from the data in this study to further expand from here and provide a relevant analysis.

Another recommendation demonstrating the possibilities of SFTs and NFTs was concert tickets and utilizing passes or consumables to leverage the blockchain to track resource consumption. Ensuring someone received and then used a pass was important to reduce fraud, ensure accountability, and improve the end-user experience. The next section covers the possibilities of how blockchain and NFT technology could help with these concepts.

Recommendation 2

Additional future research could be performed in SFTs, the ability to duplicate or consume assets on the blockchain. For example, in concert season, a venue could offer lawn seats that are all the same and offer them as SFTs since they are not unique, then mint the quantity that would be needed and sell these until they were distributed accordingly. As part of this design, a qualitative research methodology with an action research focus that could be used to determine the proper models and assessments for what should be used, analyzed, and determined. A decentralized model could help offload the resources to the blockchain, thereby relieving busy networks and fairly distributing without overloading systems and thereby saving costs. Accountability and transparency are also further provided as a mechanism for insurability and a prevention technique from duplication which is common in this industry (Cornelius, 2021). The participant data shows something easy, unique, and accessible can further be evaluated and shown as a way to allow further research to demonstrate this to make this happen.

Assets stored on the blockchain had the concept of being trackable and transparent but also are considered decentralized as a mechanism for storage. The mechanism was often not thought through as the storage was slow and did not fit all use cases described in the next recommendation.

Recommendation 3

Decentralization was also another common concept with blockchain technologies and NFTs. However, with games and NFTs the idea could be a misconception because NFTs can be tied to gaming resources that are a mix of centralized and decentralized resources. If the game services are shutdown, then the utility of the NFTs would become devalued as a result. Future research would be evaluated to understand this relationship better and identify barriers to overcome. For instance, a Decentralized Autonomous Organization (DAO) could be setup where it is in the communities hands to run the game as the publisher in addition, the game could be decentralized as a decentralized application (dApp) and allow for the community to vote to develop it and progress it. These ideas would have their own challenges as a result but could provide ways to provide a decentralized mechanism to prevent a game service from devaluing game assets. Future research would further understand all of the concepts and better understand the harmony between the concepts of these methodologies.

Conclusion

This qualitative exploratory study investigates how NFTs could be monetized and used by creating a market to provide the demand. This research study has examined this new space and seen how this could be reviewed to be developed into something useful. For example, NFTs could be used in a game world to connect users to in-game experiences, which represses a

metaverse interaction with NFTs or SFTs. A qualitative research approach is used to understand the characteristics of the social phenomena on why NFTs may or may not be more valuable as a utility in a metaverse environment as a utility (Liu et al., 2020). The study research questions would help further answer a question related to a practice-oriented problem in the field of computer science by diving into the more profound questions of the newly created area in the field of the blockchain and, more specifically, NFTs that sit on top of the blockchain. To address the study purpose, primary and sub-research questions have been developed. By reviewing these questions presented throughout the study, they provided conclusions as part of the data collected. When analyzed, they made specific inferences and comparisons that were important as part of the overall research, demonstrating credible results.

To summarize, the study's conclusions focused on how NFTs could be monetized and used by creating a market to provide the demand. From there, the sub-question of, as markets mature, comparable NFTs could be evaluated to determine the effectiveness of utility NFTs? Then also, what unique characterizations and market conditions are required? The specific qualitative research methodology selected for this study is part of what underpins this topic. The focus on qualitative methods will provide and generate new ideas for research and concepts while delivering critical determinations for providing definitive conclusions of answering the question by giving an outcome.

Looking forward to future research shows that variable identification verification is one way to further the research provided as part of the blockchain data and extend the data provided. In addition, another avenue to enhance the data provided is to evaluate the research

from a ticket distribution mindset, such as a concert venue, and provide consumers a way to handle acquiring NFTs and SFTs, and distribute tickets accordingly.

The research question that was answered from the survey questions was, how could NFTs be monetized and used by creating a market to provide the demand? This research question was divided into two sub-questions to help classify and categorize the concepts. The first sub-question is, as markets mature, could comparable NFTs be evaluated to determine the effectiveness of utility NFTs? The surveys highlighted that the long-term utility of the project is most important. At the same time, the profit potential came in second for the selection and comparison of NFTs across the market. The survey data demonstrated that NFTs could be monetized and used to create a need and provide the demand. As shown by the detailed research results in Appendix B, making NFTs with characterizations, whether existing or new, can inherently create or add on to an existing market and thereby create the demand to drive investors to the NFTs.

The second sub-question that was also reviewed was what unique characterizations and market conditions are required. Based on the results, the survey participants highlighted that as market conditions matured, their opinions would mostly not change in the reports of the NFTs that would be invested in (17 of 44). Specifically, as one individual called out, "NFTs and good project show value in time, regardless of market conditions, but of course, when the market matures, it can only benefit and not make it less valuable." The results were the same when the market deteriorated, and the overwhelming response was that no design would change (26 of 44). The results aligned from this perspective as this is telling for where NFTs, as of this study, appear not to follow what a traditional asset would follow but instead, the consumer interest in

acquiring and holding onto them would purely fall back to the overarching idea that the characterizations and project itself is more important than the market conditions. Based on the findings, NFTs can be used to create new markets and entice demand by relying on unique and limited characteristics defined throughout this research.

The problem that was addressed is how the gaming and metaverse can tie in a player's opportunity and keep someone engaged in this space. Getting a player's attention and encouraging a player to participate as part of the community by providing a sense of purpose or belonging is critical to the success of a game and will help give more value to the overall project. As demonstrated by the survey findings, participants responded that a substantial undertaking, and a sense of inclusion, would more likely entice the longer hold times of wanting to participate and encourage the participation of a project due to inclusion. This not only solves the problem of creating demand for a particular NFT project but also creates an entirely new market which allows for a longer-term mindset and content creation due to the latest entries within this market. Due to the data produced, almost any characteristic an NFT demonstrates can generate value and order; finding a relevant factor, whether historically related, music-related, meme-related, utility-related, gaming related, etc., can impact weight and build a market and demand. Overall, the blockchain and cryptocurrency, concerning asset handling, are endless, and the study was scratching the surface of the possibilities of what could be done based on the technology evaluated as of 2022.

References

- Antal, C., Cioara, T., Anghel, I., Antal, M., & Salomie, I. (2021). Distributed ledger technology review and decentralized applications development guidelines. *Future Internet*, 13(3), 62. <https://www.mdpi.com/1999-5903/13/3/62>
- Atlam, H. F., Alenezi, A., Alassafi, M. O., & Wills, G. B. (2018). Blockchain with Internet of Things: benefits, challenges, and future directions. *International Journal of Intelligent Systems and Applications*, 10(6), 40. <https://doi.org/10.5815/ijisa.2018.06.05>
- Badsha, S., Sengupta, S., Hung, L., Khalil, I., & Atiquzzaman, M. (2021). Blockchain-enabled intelligent vehicular edge computing. *IEEE Network*, 35(3), 125-131. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MNET.011.2000554>
- Bamakan Seyed Mojtaba, H., Nezhadsistani, N., Bodaghi, O., & Qu, Q. (2022). Patents and intellectual property assets as non-fungible tokens; key technologies and challenges. *Scientific Reports (Nature Publisher Group)*, 12(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-05920-6>
- Bashir, M., Afzal, M. T., & Azeem, M. (2008). Reliability and validity of qualitative and operational research paradigm. *Pakistan Journal of Statistics and Operation Research*, 4(1). <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/reliability-validity-qualitative-operational/docview/920421539/se-2>
- BAYC. (2022). *Bored Ape Yacht Club*. <https://boredapeyachtclub.com/>
- Becher, S., Gerl, A., Meier, B., & Bölz, F. (2020). Big Picture on privacy Enhancing technologies in e-Health: a holistic personal privacy workflow. *Information*, 11(7), 356. <https://doi.org/10.3390/info11070356>

- Bhargava, R. (2019a). Blockchain technology and its application: a review. *IUP Journal of Information Technology*, 15(1), 7-15. <https://doi.org/2214890794>
- Bhargava, R. (2019b). Blockchain technology and its application: a review. *IUP Journal of Information Technology*, 15(1), 7-15. <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/blockchain-technology-application-review/docview/2214890794/se-2>
- Button, S. (2018). Cryptocurrency and blockchains in emerging economies. *Software Quality Professional*, 20(3), 39-46. <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/cryptocurrency-blockchains-emerging-economies/docview/2127160917/se-2>
- Caldarelli, G. (2022). Wrapping trust for interoperability: a preliminary study of wrapped tokens. *Information*, 13(1), 6. <https://www.mdpi.com/2078-2489/13/1/6>
- Caldarelli, G., & Ellul, J. (2021). The blockchain oracle problem in decentralized finance—a multivocal approach. *Applied Sciences*, 11(16), 7572. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11167572>
- Case, T., Dick, G., Granger, M. J., & Akbulut, A. Y. (2019). Teaching information systems in the age of digital disruption. *Journal of Information Systems Education*, 30(4), 287-297. <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/teaching-information-systems-age-digital/docview/2327877243/se-2>
- Chain, B. S. (2022). *Binance smart chain GameFi hackathon*. https://www.binance.com/en/event/gamefi_hackathon?msclkid=86ab2a08a8ce11ec9850d97fc45fc67a

- Chiacchio, F., Diego, D. U., Oliveri, L. M., Spitaleri, A., Spampinato, C., & Giordano, D. (2022). A Non-Fungible Token solution for the track and trace of pharmaceutical supply chain. *Applied Sciences*, 12(8), 4019. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12084019>
- Chu, G., Li, X., Shen, D., & Zhang, Y. (2021). Stock crashes and jumps reactions to information demand and supply: an intraday analysis. *Asia - Pacific Financial Markets*, 28(3), 397-427. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10690-020-09327-z>
- Ciatto, G., Mariani, S., Omicini, A., & Zambonelli, F. (2020). From agents to blockchain: stairway to integration. *Applied Sciences*, 10(21), 7460. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10217460>
- Clohessy, T., & Acton, T. (2019). Investigating the influence of organizational factors on blockchain adoption: an innovation theory perspective [the influence of organizational factors]. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, 119(7), 1457-1491. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IMDS-08-2018-0365>
- Cocco, L. P., Andrea; Marchesi, Michele. (2017). Banking on blockchain: costs savings thanks to the blockchain technology. *Future Internet*, 9(3). <https://doi.org/10.3390/fi9030025>
- Conrad, L. Y., & Tucker, V. M. (2019). Making it tangible: hybrid card sorting within qualitative interviews [Hybrid card sorting]. *Journal of Documentation*, 75(2), 397-416. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JD-06-2018-0091>
- Cornelius, K. (2021). Betraying blockchain: accountability, transparency and document standards for Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs). *Information*, 12(9), 358. <https://doi.org/10.3390/info12090358>

- Da-Yin, L., & Wang, X. (2018). Applications of blockchain technology to logistics management in integrated casinos and entertainment. *Informatics*, 5(4), 44.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/informatics5040044>
- Davis, A., Murphy, J., Owens, D., Khazanchi, D., & Zigurs, I. (2009). Avatars, people, and virtual worlds: foundations for research in Metaverses. *Journal of the Association for Information Systems*, 10(2), 90-117. <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/avatars-people-virtual-worlds-foundations/docview/198832667/se-2>
- De Domenico, M. B., Andrea. (2019). The fragility of decentralised trustless socio-technical systems. *EPJ Data Science*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.1140/epjds/s13688-018-0180-6>
- Dong, N., Bai, G., Lung-Chen, H., Edmund Kok Heng, L., & Jin Song, D. (2020). A blockchain-based decentralized booking system. *The Knowledge Engineering Review*, 35.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0269888920000260>
- Dospinescu, O., & Caramangiu, M. E. (2018). The key success factors for an M-Learning cryptocurrency application. *Informatica Economica*, 22(2), 14-24.
<https://doi.org/10.12948/issn14531305/22.2.2018.02>
- Dutka, P. M. S. N. R. N. C. N. N., & Astroth, K. S. P. R. N. (2022). Navigating the institutional review board process. *Nephrology Nursing Journal*, 49(1), 67-71.
<https://doi.org/10.37526/1526-744X.2022.49.1.67>
- Es-Samaali, H., Outchakoucht, A., & Leroy, J. P. (2017). A blockchain-based access control for big data. *International Journal of Computer Networks and Communications Security*, 5(7), 137-147. <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/blockchain-based-access-control-big-data/docview/1931135846/se-2>

- Everest, T. (2021). Philosophical paradigms as the bases for knowledge management research and practice. *Knowledge Management & E-Learning*, 13(2), 209-224.
<https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/philosophical-paradigms-as-bases-knowledge/docview/2559469688/se-2>
- Fang, Y., Zhaolong, J., Jin, Z., Xie, X., Lu, Y., & Li, T. (2021). Fast policy interpretation and dynamic conflict resolution for blockchain-based IoT system. *Wireless Communications & Mobile Computing (Online)*, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/9968743>
- Feng, L. Z., Hui; Chen, Yong; Lou, Liqi. (2018). Scalable dynamic multi-agent practical Byzantine fault-tolerant consensus in permissioned blockchain. *Applied Sciences*, 8(10).
<https://doi.org/10.3390/app8101919>
- Francesca Dal, M., Dicuonzo, G., Massaro, M., & Dell'Atti, V. (2020). Smart contracts to enable sustainable business models. A case study [Smart contracts to sustainable business models]. *Management Decision*, 58(8), 1601-1619. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MD-09-2019-1266>
- Fremantle, P., & Scott, P. (2017). A survey of secure middleware for the Internet of Things. *PeerJ Computer Science*. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.114>
- Gatteschi, V. L., Fabrizio; Demartini, Claudio; Pranteda, Chiara; Santamaría, Víctor. (2018). Blockchain and smart contracts for insurance: is the technology mature enough? *Future Internet*, 10(2). <https://doi.org/10.3390/fi10020020>
- Goldston, J., Chaffer, T. J., & Martinez, G. (2022). The Metaverse as the digital leviathan: a case study of Bit.Country. *The Journal of Applied Business and Economics*, 24(2), 40-59.

<https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/metaverse-as-digital-leviathan-case-study-bit/docview/2647409326/se-2>

Governatori, G., Idelberger, F., Milosevic, Z., Riveret, R., Sartor, G., & Xu, X. (2018). On legal contracts, imperative and declarative smart contracts, and blockchain systems. *Artificial Intelligence and Law*, 26(4), 377-409. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10506-018-9223-3>

Guerra, M. L., Sorini, L., & Stefanini, L. (2020). Bitcoin analysis and forecasting through fuzzy transform. *Axioms*, 9(4), 139. <https://doi.org/10.3390/axioms9040139>

Han, Y., Li, X., Feng, Z., Jin, R., Kangwa, J., & Obas John, E. (2022). Grounded theory and social psychology approach to investigating the formation of construction workers' unsafe behaviour. *Computational Intelligence and Neuroscience : CIN*, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/3581563>

Heo, H., & Shin, S. (2021). Understanding block and transaction logs of permissionless blockchain networks. *Security and Communication Networks*, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/9549602>

Hosseinian, H., Shahinzadeh, H., Gharehpetian, G. B., Azani, Z., & Shaneh, M. (2020). Blockchain outlook for deployment of IoT in distribution networks and smart homes. *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, 10(3), 2787-2796. <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/blockchain-outlook-deployment-iot-distribution/docview/2368786791/se-2>

Huang, T. (2021). Resource sharing of smart city based on blockchain. *Wireless Communications & Mobile Computing (Online)*, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/5886024>

- Hudson, R., & Urquhart, A. (2019). Technical trading and cryptocurrencies. *Annals of Operations Research*, 1-30. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10479-019-03357-1>
- Islam, S., Badsha, S., Sengupta, S., La, H., Khalil, I., & Atiquzzaman, M. (2021). Blockchain-enabled intelligent vehicular edge computing. *IEEE Network*, 35(3), 125-131. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MNET.011.2000554>
- Jagger, B., & Abu-Mahfouz, A. M. (2022). Connect2NFT: a web-Based, blockchain enabled NFT application with the aim of reducing fraud and ensuring authenticated social, non-human verified digital identity. *Mathematics*, 10(21), 3934. <https://doi.org/10.3390/math10213934>
- Jeng, W., & He, D. (2022). Surveying research data-sharing practices in US social sciences: a knowledge infrastructure-inspired conceptual framework. *Online Information Review*, 46(7), 1275-1292. <https://doi.org/10.1108/OIR-03-2020-0079>
- Jiang, N., Bai, F., Huang, L., An, Z., & Shen, T. (2022). Reputation-driven dynamic node consensus and reliability sharding model in IoT blockchain. *Algorithms*, 15(2), 28. <https://doi.org/10.3390/a15020028>
- Jin, J.-H. E., Hyun-Min; Lee, Myung-Joon. (2019). Bspace: a group workspace over the Ethereum blockchain with off-blockchain storage. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Research*, 9(40), 53-60. <https://doi.org/10.19101/IJACR.COM16003>
- Jung, H. (2021). Blockchain implementation method for interoperability between CBDCs. *Future Internet*, 13(5), 133. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fi13050133>

- Justic, U. S. D. o. (2022). *Two defendants charged in Non-Fungible Token (“NFT”) fraud And money laundering scheme*. https://www.justice.gov/usao-sdny/pr/two-defendants-charged-non-fungible-token-nft-fraud-and-money-laundering-scheme-0#_ftn1
- Kamišalić, A., Kramberger, R., & Iztok, F. (2021). Synergy of blockchain technology and data mining techniques for anomaly detection. *Applied Sciences*, 11(17), 7987. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11177987>
- Kampik, T., & Najjar, A. (2020). Simulating, off-chain and on-chain: agent-based simulations in cross-organizational business processes. *Information*, 11(1), 34. <https://doi.org/10.3390/info11010034>
- Karbasi, A. H., & Shahpasand, S. (2020). A post-quantum end-to-end encryption over smart contract-based blockchain for defeating man-in-the-middle and interception attacks. *Peer-To-Peer Networking and Applications*, 13(5), 1423-1441. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12083-020-00901-w>
- Kassem, J. A. S. S. M.-G., Hector; Pervez, Zeeshan; Dahal, Keshav. (2019). DNS-IdM: A blockchain identity management system to secure personal data sharing in a network. *Applied Sciences*, 9(15). <https://doi.org/10.3390/app9152953>
- Kauflin, J. (2022). *Why Jack Dorsey’s first-tweet NFT plummeted 99% in value in a year*. Forbes. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/jeffkauflin/2022/04/14/why-jack-dorseys-first-tweet-nft-plummeted-99-in-value-in-a-year/?sh=2677332a65cb>
- Ke, X., Wagner, C., & Du, H. S. (2022). Calling for information systems research on Esports: an overview study. *Communications of the Association for Information Systems*, 50. <https://doi.org/10.17705/1CAIS.05010>

Khan, D., Low Tang, J., & Manzoor Ahmed, H. (2021). Systematic literature review of challenges in blockchain scalability. *Applied Sciences*, 11(20), 9372.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/app11209372>

Kim, H., Kim, K., Kwon, H., & Seo, H. (2020). ASIC-resistant Proof of Work based on power analysis of low-end microcontrollers. *Mathematics*, 8(8), 1343.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/math8081343>

Knirsch, F. U., Andreas; Engel, Dominik. (2019). Implementing a blockchain from scratch: why, how, and what we learned. *EURASIP Journal on Information Security*, 2019(1), 1-14.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13635-019-0085-3>

Konashevych, O. (2020). Cross-blockchain protocol for public registries. *International Journal of Web Information Systems*, 16(5), 571-610. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJWIS-07-2020-0045>

Kortesniemi, Y. L., Dmitrij; Elo, Tommi; Fotiou, Nikos. (2019). Improving the privacy of IoT with Decentralised Identifiers (DIDs). *Journal of Computer Networks and Communications*, 2019(2019), 10. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/8706760>

Kuzma, M., Bačić, K., Lea, S.-K., & Sužnjević, M. (2022). Predicting player churn of a Free-to-Play mobile video game using supervised machine learning. *Applied Sciences*, 12(6), 2795.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/app12062795>

Leon, N. I. D., Bhatt, S. K., & Al-Jumaily, A. (2014). Augmented reality game based multi-usage rehabilitation therapist for stroke patients. *International Journal on Smart Sensing and Intelligent Systems*, 7(3), 1044-1058. <https://doi.org/10.21307/ijssis-2017-693>

- Li, Q., Hou, J., Meng, S., & Long, H. (2020). GLIDE: A game theory and data-driven mimicking linkage intrusion detection for edge computing networks. *Complexity*, 2020, 18. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/7136160>
- Li, W., Wu, J., Cao, J., Chen, N., Zhang, Q., & Buyya, R. (2021). Blockchain-based trust management in cloud computing systems: a taxonomy, review and future directions. *Journal of Cloud Computing*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13677-021-00247-5>
- Liao, D.-Y., & Wang, X. (2018). Applications of blockchain technology to logistics management in integrated casinos and entertainment. *Informatics*, 5(4), 44. <https://www.mdpi.com/2227-9709/5/4/44>
- Liu, C., Gao, J., Li, Y., Wang, H., & Chen, Z. (2020). Studying gas exceptions in blockchain-based cloud applications. *Journal of Cloud Computing*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13677-020-00176-9>
- Liu, Q. Z., Xiao. (2019). Research on trust mechanism of cooperation innovation with big data processing based on blockchain. *EURASIP Journal on Wireless Communications and Networking*, 2019, 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13638-019-1340-5>
- Liu Xiao, F., Huan-Huan, R., Si-Hao, L., & Xian-Jian, J. (2021). Characterizing key agents in the cryptocurrency economy through blockchain transaction analysis. *EPJ Data Science*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1140/epjds/s13688-021-00276-9>
- Mahato, B., Guha, R. D., & De, D. (2021). Distributed bandwidth selection approach for cooperative peer to peer multi-cloud platform. *Peer-To-Peer Networking and Applications*, 14(1), 177-201. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12083-020-00917-2>

- Mamais, S. S. T., George. (2017). Behavioural Verification: Preventing Report Fraud in Decentralized Advert Distribution System. *Future Internet*, 9(4).
<https://doi.org/10.3390/fi9040088>
- Marshall, B., Cardon, P., Poddar, A., & Fontenot, R. (2013). Does sample size matter in qualitative research?: a review of qualitative interviews interviews in IS research. *The Journal of Computer Information Systems*, 54(1), 11-22.
<https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/does-sample-size-matter-qualitative-research/docview/1471047612/se-2>
- Menghui, L., Dong, X., Cao, Z., & Shen, J. (2021). SESCOF: a secure and efficient supply chain framework via blockchain-based smart contracts. *Security and Communication Networks*, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/8884478>
- Moiling, G., Klein, A., Hoppen, N., & Rosa, R. D. (2020). Cryptocurrency: a mine of controversies. *Journal of Information Systems and Technology Management : JISTEM*, 17, 1-15.
<https://doi.org/10.4301/S1807-1775202017010>
- Muddasar, A., & Bagui, S. (2021). Introduction to NFTs: the future of digital collectibles. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, 12(10).
<https://doi.org/10.14569/IJACSA.2021.0121007>
- Nandi, S., Sarkis, J., Hervani, A., & Helms, M. (2021). Do blockchain and circular economy practices improve post COVID-19 supply chains? A resource-based and resource dependence perspective [Blockchain and circular economy practices]. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, 121(2), 333-363. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IMDS-09-2020-0560>

- Ojog, S. (2021). The emerging world of decentralized finance. *Informatica Economica*, 25(4), 43-52. <https://doi.org/10.24818/issn14531305/25.4.2021.05>
- Ourzik, V. Y. (2022). Customer knowledge management: a systematic literature review and agenda for future research. In (Vol. 2, pp. 1384-1394,R1336). Kidmore End: Academic Conferences International Limited. <https://www.proquest.com/conference-papers-proceedings/customer-knowledge-management-systematic/docview/2734336351/se-2>
- Paajala, I., Nyysölä, J., Mattila, J., & Karppinen, P. (2022). Users' perceptions of key blockchain features in games. *Future Internet*, 14(11), 321. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fi14110321>
- Palaiokrassas, G., Skoufis, P., Voutyras, O., Kawasaki, T., Gallissot, M., Azzabi, R., Tsuge, A., Litke, A., Okoshi, T., Nakazawa, J., & Varvarigou, T. (2021). Combining blockchains, smart contracts, and complex sensors management platform for hyper-connected SmartCities: an IoT data marketplace use case. *Computers*, 10(10), 133. <https://doi.org/10.3390/computers10100133>
- Palma, S. T., Damian; Pareschi, Remo; Cerrone, Carmine; Willem-Jan van den Heuvel. (2018). Business-savvy blockchains with gamification: a framework for collaborative problem solving. *EAI Endorsed Transactions on Serious Games*, 5(16). <https://doi.org/10.4108/eai.13-7-2018.155567>
- Palmisano, T., Convertini, V. N., Sarcinella, L., Luigia, G., & Bonifazi, M. (2022). Notarization and anti-plagiarism: a new blockchain approach. *Applied Sciences*, 12(1), 243. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12010243>

- Pappalardo, G. T. D. M. C., Guido; Aste, Tomaso. (2018). Blockchain inefficiency in the Bitcoin peers network. *EPJ Data Science*, 7(1), 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1140/epjds/s13688-018-0159-3>
- Park, A., Kietzmann, J., Pitt, L., & Dabirian, A. (2022). The evolution of Nonfungible Tokens: complexity and novelty of NFT use-cases. *IT Professional Magazine*, 24(1), 9-14. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MITP.2021.3136055>
- Park, Y., Sur, C., & Rhee, K.-H. (2018). A secure incentive scheme for vehicular delay tolerant networks using cryptocurrency. *Security and Communication Networks*, 2018, 13. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/5932183>
- Pinto-Gutiérrez, C., Gaitán, S., Jaramillo, D., & Velasquez, S. (2022). The NFT hype: what draws attention to Non-Fungible tokens? *Mathematics*, 10(3), 335. <https://doi.org/10.3390/math10030335>
- Prasad, B., & Ramachandram, S. (2021). Vulnerabilities and attacks on smart contracts over blockChain. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education*, 12(11), 5436-5449. <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/vulnerabilities-attacks-on-smart-contracts-over/docview/2639743481/se-2>
- Predescu, A., Arsene, D., Pahonțu, B., Mocanu, M., & Chiru, C. (2021). A serious gaming approach for crowdsensing in urban water infrastructure with blockchain support. *Applied Sciences*, 11(4), 1449. <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-3417/11/4/1449>
- Qasim Ali Arain; Memon, I. D., Zhongliang; Muhammad Hammad Memon; Farman Ali Mangi; Zubedi, Asma. (2018). For the pet care appliance of location aware infrastructure on

cyber physical system. *Computers--Computer Graphics*, 77(5).

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-017-4469-4>

Rajguru, S. (2021, 2021 Nov 27). Why crypto is a natural evolution of old money. *CIOL*.

<https://www.proquest.com/magazines/why-crypto-is-natural-evolution-old-money/docview/2604478919/se-2>

Reyes-Menendez, A., Jose Ramon, S., & Ferrão, F. (2019). The importance of behavioral data to identify online fake reviews for tourism businesses: a systematic review. *PeerJ Computer Science*. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.219>

Risius, M. S., Kai. (2017). A blockchain research framework. *Business & Information Systems Engineering*, 59(6), 385-409. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12599-017-0506-0>

Rossi, M., Mueller-Bloch, C., Thatcher, J. B., & Beck, R. (2019). Blockchain research in information systems: current trends and an inclusive future research agenda. *Journal of the Association for Information Systems*, 20(9), 1388-1403.

<https://doi.org/10.17705/1jais.00571>

Rotună, C. G., Alexandru; Zamfiroiu, Alin; Anagrama, Dragoş Smada. (2019). Smart city ecosystem using blockchain technology. *Informatica Economica*, 23(4), 41-50.

<https://doi.org/10.12948/issn14531305/23.4.2019.04>

Salminen, J., Soon-gyo, J., Kamel, A., Froneman, W., & Jansen, B. J. (2022). Who is in the sample? An analysis of real and surrogate users as participants in user study research in the information technology fields. *PeerJ Computer Science*.

<https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.1136>

Sandstrom, G. (2022). Interview: blockchain and digital transformation in financial services.

Technology Innovation Management Review, 12(1/2), 1-9.

<https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/interview-blockchain-digital-transformation/docview/2684211487/se-2>

Sarkintudu, S. I., Huda; Abd Wahab, Alawiyah. (2019). Cryptocurrency platform ecosystem: a systematic literature review from information systems perspective. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Research*, 9(44), 308-315. <https://doi.org/10.19101/IJACR.PID97>

Shen, B., Tan, W., Guo, J., Zhao, L., & Peng, Q. (2021). How to promote user purchase in Metaverse? A systematic literature review on consumer behavior research and virtual commerce application design. *Applied Sciences*, 11(23), 11087.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/app112311087>

Shen, B. G., Jingzhi; Yang, Yilong. (2019). MedChain: efficient healthcare data sharing via blockchain. *Applied Sciences*, 9(6). <https://doi.org/10.3390/app9061207>

Shrestha, A. K., Vassileva, J., Joshi, S., & Just, J. (2021). Augmenting the technology acceptance model with trust model for the initial adoption of a blockchain-based system. *PeerJ Computer Science*. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.502>

Skinner, R. J., Nelson, R. R., & Chin, W. (2022). Synthesizing qualitative evidence: a roadmap for information systems research. *Journal of the Association for Information Systems*, 23(3), 639-677. <https://doi.org/10.17705/1jais.00741>

Stoica, M. G.-M., Bogdan; Mircea, Marinela. (2019). Restarting the information society based on blockchain technology. *Informatica Economica*, 23(3), 39-48.

<https://doi.org/10.12948/issn14531305/23.3.2019.04>

- Subramanian, H., Cousins, K., Bouyad, L. B., Sheth, A., & Conway, D. (2020). Blockchain regulations and decentralized applications: panel report from AMCIS 2018. *Communications of the Association for Information Systems*, 47, 9. <https://doi.org/10.17705/1CAIS.04709>
- Taherdoost, H. (2022). A critical review of blockchain acceptance models—blockchain technology adoption frameworks and applications. *Computers*, 11(2), 24. <https://doi.org/10.3390/computers11020024>
- Tanaka, K., & Evans, R. (2020). Sana: A Gamified Rehabilitation Management System for Anterior Cruciate Ligament Reconstruction Recovery. *Applied Sciences*, 10(14), 4868. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10144868>
- Tomita, K., Husa, A., Zhu, M., Ergulec, F., Lachheb, A., & Boling, E. (2021). Challenges implementing qualitative research methods in a study of instructional design practice. *TechTrends*, 65(2), 144-151. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11528-020-00569-2>
- Underhill, R. G. (1995). How can we improve the credibility and status of qualitative research studies? *School Science and Mathematics*, 95(3), 113. <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/how-can-we-improve-credibility-status-qualitative/docview/195203771/se-2>
- Valeonti, F., Bikakis, A., Terras, M., Speed, C., Hudson-Smith, A., & Chalkias, K. (2021). Crypto collectibles, museum funding and OpenGLAM: challenges, opportunities and the potential of Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs). *Applied Sciences*, 11(21), 9931. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11219931>

Vasan, K., Milán, J., & Albert-László, B. (2022). Quantifying NFT-driven networks in crypto art.

Scientific Reports (Nature Publisher Group), 12(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-05146-6>

Victor. (2021). *Explore the NFT games sector with DEEPSPACE \$DPS*. Altcoin Buzz.

<https://www.altcoinbuzz.io/blockchain-gaming/game-launches-updates/explode-the-nft-games-sector-with-deepspace-dps/>

voanews. (2021). 'NFT' named 'word of the year' for 2021.

<https://www.voanews.com/a/nftnamed-word-of-the-year-for-2021/6326462.html>

Wagner, R., & Cozmiuc, D. (2022). Extended reality in marketing—a multiple case study on

Internet of Things Platforms. *Information*, 13(6), 278.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/info13060278>

Wang, L., Liu, X., & Lin, X. (2021). A fair and privacy-preserving image trading system based on blockchain and group signature. *Security and Communication Networks; London*.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2021/5701258>

Wang, Y., Li, J., Liu, W., & Tan, A. (2021). Efficient concurrent execution of smart Contracts in Blockchain Sharding. *Security and Communication Networks*, 2021.

<https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/6688168>

Weingärtner, T., Batista, D., Köchli, S., & Voutat, G. (2021). Prototyping a smart contract based public procurement to fight corruption. *Computers*, 10(7), 85.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/computers10070085>

- Wu, Y., Tan, X., & Lu, T. (2020). A new multiple-distribution GAN model to solve complexity in end-to-end chromosome karyotyping. *Complexity*, 2020, 15.
<https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/8923838>
- Xiaoyu Ma, J. Z., Xiumei Yang, and Guangyuan Liu. (2020). A blockchain voting system based on the feedback mechanism and Wilson Score. *Information*, 11(12), 552.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/info11120552>
- Xie, J., Lu, H., Lele, K., & Cheng, Y. (2022). Citing criteria and its effects on researcher's intention to cite: A mixed-method study. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 73(8), 1079-1091. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.24614>
- Xie, P. (2019). The effect of incentive hierarchy system of social media in the delivery of quality information. *Journal of International Technology and Information Management*, 28(4), 1-26. <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/effect-incentive-hierarchy-system-social-media/docview/2419752027>
- Xu, Q., Chao, J., Mohamed Faruq Bin Mohamed, R., Bharadwaj, V., & Khin Mi Mi, A. (2018). Blockchain-based decentralized content trust for docker images. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, 77(14), 18223-18248. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-017-5224-6>
- Xu, X., Chen, Y., Yuan, Y., Huang, T., Zhang, X., & Lianyong, Q. (2020). Blockchain-based cloudlet management for multimedia workflow in mobile cloud computing. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, 79(15-16), 9819-9844. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-019-07900-x>
- Yang, B. (2022). Prevention of business risks of internet information security platforms based on blockchain technology. *Computational Intelligence and Neuroscience : CIN*, 2022.
<https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/7671810>

- Yang, J. M. M. H. O. N.-Y., Lee; Mohiuddin, Ahmed; Chul-Soo, Kim. (2019). Proof-of-Familiarity: a privacy-preserved blockchain scheme for collaborative medical decision-making. *Applied Sciences*, 9(7). <https://doi.org/10.3390/app9071370>
- Yao-Chieh, H., Ting-Ting, L., Chatzopoulos, D., & Pan, H. (2020). Analyzing smart contract interactions and contract level state consensus. *Concurrency and Computation*, 32(12). <https://doi.org/10.1002/cpe.5228>
- Yiu, N. (2021). Toward blockchain-enabled supply chain anti-counterfeiting and traceability. *Future Internet*, 13(4), 86. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fi13040086>
- Yuan, R. Y.-B., Xia; Hai-Bo Chen; Bin-Yu, Zang; Xie, Jan. (2018). ShadowEth: private smart contract on public blockchain. *Journal of Computer Science and Technology*, 33(3), 542-556. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11390-018-1839-y>
- Zamani, E., & Giaglis, G. (2018). With a little help from the miners: distributed ledger technology and market disintermediation. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, 118(3), 637-652. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IMDS-05-2017-0231>
- Zhang, A., & Lin, X. (2018). Towards secure and privacy-preserving data sharing in e-Health systems via consortium blockchain. *Journal of Medical Systems*, 42(8), 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10916-018-0995-5>
- Zhang, H., & Xiao, J. (2019). Quality assessment framework for open government data: Meta-synthesis of qualitative research, 2009-2019. *The Electronic Library*, 38(2), 209-222. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EL-06-2019-0145>

- Zhang, J., Hassandoust, F., & Williams, J. (2020). Online customer trust in the context of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). *Pacific Asia Journal of the Association for Information Systems*, 12(1), 4. <https://doi.org/10.17705/1pais.12104>
- Zhou, L., & Miguel Baptista, N. (2013). Doing qualitative research in Chinese contexts: Lessons learned from conducting interviews in a Chinese healthcare environment. *Library Hi Tech*, 31(3), 419-434. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LHT-11-2012-0104>

Appendix A: Survey Questions

NFT Collection Questions

IRB Consent Sample Form

(Note: will process / cleanup into Google Form as part of a disclosure)

I am asking you to participate in a research study titled “Non-Fungible Tokens Value with Metaverse and Blockchain Gaming”.

What the study is about

The purpose of this qualitative exploratory study is to determine how NFTs can be monetized and used by creating a market to provide the demand. This research study will examine this new space and see how this could be reviewed to be developed into something useful.

What we will ask you to do

I will ask you to fill out the Google Survey to the best of your ability as accurately as possible.

The survey should take about 10-15 minutes maximum of your time.

Risks and discomforts

If there are no known risks, state: I do not anticipate any risks from participating in this research.

Benefits

I hope to learn from this research additional knowledge for the research community to study how individuals think when selecting NFTs and consider deciding to hold an NFT for value. When determining a particular NFT for value, whether it is of specific interest, such as a music NFT, a piece of artwork, gaming, intrinsic value, or just a random shot in the dark, or has some particular utility attached to it.

Compensation for participation

As part of participating and taking the time to complete the survey, participants will receive an NFT token.

Privacy/Confidentiality/Data Security

Participant's data and privacy are critical and essential, and the following items are going to be taken into effect as part of the survey:

- *No collection of personal data (anonymous survey)*
- *De-identification of data*
- *Physical security of data is behind MFA and in secured cloud storage*
- *The researcher and the organizing university will have access to the anonymous information*

- *The data will be stored in the cloud storage for up to 7 years and then destroyed accordingly*
- *Note: Data may exist on backups and server logs beyond the timeframe of this research project.*

Taking part is voluntary

This research study is entirely voluntary, and the participant may refuse to participate before the survey begins or discontinue at any time.

Data collected within this form is anonymized, and no personal information is collected or shared as part of this research. In addition, data is kept and stored for up to 7 years for further research. By continuing you agree to these statements and agree you will provide accurate responses to ensure fair research assessments.

Click I Approve if you agree to the above

[Consent Included]

[Note the below questions will be translated to a Google Form]

Candidate Number (Randomly Assigned on Google Sheet)

1. What is your age?

2. Rate your experience with interacting with cryptocurrency

(I never Interacted with it) 1 ----- 5 (occasionally work with it) ----- 10 (Work with it every day)

3. Rate your experience with interacting with Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs)

(I never Interacted with it) 1 ----- 5 (occasionally work with it) ----- 10 (Work with it every day)

4. As part of reviewing the market for NFTs, what characteristics are important in an NFT?

(Select all the apply)

Limited

Indivisible

Unique

Ownership

Fraud Proof

Other

5. In what market conditions would you consider buying NFTs?

(select all that apply)

Financing

Interest Rates

Asset Prices

Inflationary / Deflationary

Capacity

Inventory

Competition

Business Models

Consumer Demand

Business Demand

Employment

Procurement

Taxes & Regulations

Stability

6. When a market matures, do the characteristics of NFTs that you are looking for change?
7. As market conditions deteriorate, does your NFT investment strategy change?
8. Have you participated in a pre-listing of an NFT?
Yes / No
9. What factors did you consider for participating?
10. What sources do you consider to be reliable to when deciding to acquire an NFT?

Friends

Celebrity Endorsements

Influencers

Media publications

Other

11. When creating a new market for NFTs, what would you look for in the NFTs to want to acquire them?

12. Hypothetically, if you are project creator of an NFT, what are some tasks you would do to create demand?

13. In one sentence, describe what you look for when acquiring an NFT

14. Would you consider yourself a gamer?

Yes // No

15. What interests you when selecting an NFT to acquire?

MEME (trending NFTs)

Utility NFTs

Art NFTs

Music NFTs

Collectible NFTs

16. Interest in purchasing an NFT

Already purchased

Close to making a purchase

Saving for a purchase

Not interested

17. Provide a summary of your thoughts on interacting with an NFT in a hybrid environment versus just holding an NFT in a digital wallet and your interests in the two digital assets.

18. What blockchain do you consider when acquiring an NFT?

Ethereum / Solana / Binance / Polygon / Flow / Cardano / Other

19. What marketplace(s) do you use to buy or sell NFTs?

20. What platform do you use to trade NFTs?

PC / Mobile / Other

21. When determining an NFT to acquire, what is the essential attribute?

Floor Price // Rarity Score // Hype/Influence /// Endorsement /// Future Utility //

Community // Artistic Value /// Other

22. What is the reason to acquire an NFT?

Sell within 3 months

/// sell within 6 months // sell with 12 months //

hold I'm not selling

23. What type of NFT is important to you?

Metaverse Gaming NFTs //// Profile Pictures NFTs /// Art NFTs // Music NFTs // Others

ProQuest Number: 30247079

INFORMATION TO ALL USERS

The quality and completeness of this reproduction is dependent on the quality and completeness of the copy made available to ProQuest.

Distributed by ProQuest LLC (2023).

Copyright of the Dissertation is held by the Author unless otherwise noted.

This work may be used in accordance with the terms of the Creative Commons license or other rights statement, as indicated in the copyright statement or in the metadata associated with this work. Unless otherwise specified in the copyright statement or the metadata, all rights are reserved by the copyright holder.

This work is protected against unauthorized copying under Title 17, United States Code and other applicable copyright laws.

Microform Edition where available © ProQuest LLC. No reproduction or digitization of the Microform Edition is authorized without permission of ProQuest LLC.

ProQuest LLC
789 East Eisenhower Parkway
P.O. Box 1346
Ann Arbor, MI 48106 - 1346 USA